

UNCONDITIONAL CASH TRANSFERS IN INDIA

Tracing
the journey,
Shaping
the *future*

FOREWORD

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BY

WITH

PROJECT DEEP

www.project-deep.org

Project DEEP is the only nonprofit in India focussed on strengthening cash-based policies, to enable an increase in the per capita income of the bottom 20% in the country. We are using evidence-based approaches to re-imagine the design and delivery of cash-based policies, which can empower communities and stimulate inclusive growth. Extensive community work through pilots in five locations has built our foundational understanding of the model and its impact on communities. We are now using our learnings from the field to engage with policymakers to boost the effectiveness and sustainability of the INR 2,80,000 crore already being allocated to unconditional cash transfers.

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BUILDING THE WELFARE STATE

Under ideal conditions, the two fundamental theorems of welfare economics offer a coherent framework for public policy. The first asserts that competitive markets, when undistorted, lead to an efficient allocation of resources. The second holds that if the resulting distribution is socially undesirable, it can be corrected through a redistribution of initial endowments, without sacrificing efficiency. However, for either theorem to hold in practice, certain foundational public goods must be in place, such as a well-functioning legal system, effective law enforcement, and macroeconomic stability. Together, these three elements—the two welfare theorems and the provision of canonical public goods—form the foundational pillars on which modern welfare-oriented economies are expected to stand. Within such a framework, the role of the state is to focus on delivering these public goods and facilitating redistribution through transfers from high to low-income populations.

However, ideal conditions rarely prevail, and several challenges must be addressed in any country's journey toward building a well-functioning welfare state. These include market failures, primarily due to high information asymmetry and distorted consumer preferences in fields such as healthcare and primary education; distortions created by the state through persistent intervention in areas such as manufacturing, financial services, and energy, where markets have become viable; and a lack of clarity on effective transfer mechanisms.

Addressing these will require governments to follow a strategic and politically sensitive roadmap comprising the following steps:

- ✦ **Diagnose and Sequence:** Classify all major subsidies and state-owned enterprises (SOEs) by their efficiency, equity, and necessity, and begin with the most regressive and elite-captured areas (such as fertiliser, energy, and credit).
- ✦ **Compensate and Institutionalise:** Introduce carefully structured transfer programs and gradually scale them up as fiscal space opens further, framing the shift as an investment in people, not in unproductive firms or commodities. Finally, use social registries, expenditure caps, and sunset clauses to formalise reform.

This approach will build public trust and administrative capacity without fiscal shocks. It will also help prevent reform fatigue or backlash, especially in democracies. While this is a challenging process, there are several examples of developed and developing economies that have successfully made these transitions. A particularly notable one is that of Brazil, where *Bolsa Família* replaced distortionary subsidies with targeted cash transfers, thereby reducing inequality without compromising fiscal discipline.

THE CASE FOR UCTS

Once distortions are addressed, the next frontier is ensuring that redistribution is achieved through the most efficient and dignified instruments available. As a means to accomplish this, Unconditional Cash Transfers (UCTs) embody the ideal of a non-distortionary redistribution. Unlike subsidies or conditional programs, they do not alter relative prices or impose behavioural conditions. They are administratively simple, scalable through digital infrastructure, and politically attractive when framed as rights-based entitlements. UCTs respect individual agency, improve psychological well-being, and enhance resilience. They make the equity component of the second welfare theorem practically realisable without compromising the allocative logic of the first. India has already made significant investments over the past decade in building the infrastructure, technology, and administrative systems needed to implement UCTs at scale. Today, nearly 11% of total social sector spending—amounting to approximately ₹2.8 lakh crore—is allocated to such schemes across diverse beneficiary groups.

Key priorities for the future include more accurate identification of vulnerable households, taking particular care to avoid exclusions; improving the accessibility and reliability of payment channels, including through digital platforms such as payment banks; strengthening safeguards against fraud; and streamlining the high-touch processes of enrollment and verification currently required to receive benefits. To support the broader acceptance of much larger transfer programmes, it is also essential to address concerns that lack empirical support but continue to influence perceptions, such as fears of increased substance use or reduced motivation to work among recipients.

This report lays the foundation for dispelling these myths through evidence and also provides a consolidated view of the evolution of this model in our country, along with best practices adopted by States. It also extends an invitation to civil society and policymakers to come together to address these questions and establish UCTs as a strong tool for inclusive and dignified development.

THE VISION FOR THE FUTURE

The welfare state of the future will not be defined by sprawling subsidies or ownership of production, but by its ability to deliver security, agency, and opportunity through well-governed, targeted, and flexible instruments.

UCTs are central to this vision. They represent not just a technical fix, but a philosophical shift: from paternalism to trust, from distortion to dignity. As countries grapple with fiscal constraints, climate transitions, and technological change, UCTs offer a powerful platform to re-anchor state capacity around what matters most: *the people*.

FOUNDER'S NOTE

PANKHURI SHAH
Co-founder, Project DEEP

In 2023, we started Project DEEP with a strong conviction that giving cash works!

Since then, our belief has only been further validated by both global evidence and the experience of impact through our own programmes. What has also changed is the policy landscape, with unconditional cash transfers (UCTs) cementing their place as a promising tool within the welfare portfolio.

MUZAMIL BAIG
Co-founder, Project DEEP

However, the conversation around 'free money' continues to polarise people. There is a significant knowledge gap around the various types of direct cash transfers (DCTs), the unconditional nature of the more recent schemes, and their impact. The lack of a comprehensive, nationwide analysis on the evolution and landscape of cash-based policies makes policymakers and other relevant stakeholders reliant on fragmented data that subsequently leads to siloed efforts, inconsistent approaches to similar goals, and missed opportunities for cross-learning and collaboration within India.

Since 2019, the number of government-backed UCTs has tripled. Today, over 70 such schemes are being implemented across 18 Indian states, for a diverse range of demographic groups. This growing emphasis on UCTs also aligns with global interest in basic income as a strategy to reduce income inequality, cushion households from income shocks, and alleviate extreme poverty.

It is an opportune moment to consolidate our understanding of this welfare tool and to set a common stakeholder-wise agenda to ensure that the way forward is intentional and impactful.

This report aims to provide a systematic, context-sensitive analysis of UCTs in India. It addresses four critical areas that, to date, have not been comprehensively examined. Firstly, it examines how UCTs have been prioritised under Central and state budgets relative to the overall fiscal expenditure on welfare provisions in the last decade. Secondly, it explores the design of UCT schemes in India. This is done using Project DEEP's F.A.C.T. Framework that was developed from our own field experience. Thirdly, it also outlines the challenges that continue to persist in implementation, and extrapolates best practices India and abroad to inform the future of cash transfer schemes. Lastly, it calls out the need for evidence-based evaluations of past and ongoing schemes to strengthen policymaking and implementation.

METHODOLOGY

- ✦ We collected **secondary data** from the public domain to understand the current discourse on UCTs both, in India and abroad. This included **a literature review** to classify the different types of tools that are commonly used for welfare with a particular focus on distinguishing UCTs from other DCTs. We also gathered **case studies** from various countries, including India. We also collected case studies from various

countries to provide key learnings for the Indian context.

- ✦ We collected **budgetary data** on all the UCTs in India from 2014-15 to 2024-25 including, when available, data on their objectives, target recipients, amount disbursed, and total fiscal expenditure. While we were able to identify over 70 schemes, their budgetary data is patchy, with information available for only 41 of them in 2024-25.
- ✦ Furthermore, we have compared different aspects of UCTs to other **macro and micro economic indicators** like fiscal expenditure, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), debt level, Monthly Per Capita Expenditure (MPCE), and state-level indicators including total welfare spending to provide a granular analysis of how UCTs are faring as welfare tools.
- ✦ We also conducted **21 in-depth interviews** with a diverse experts. These included practitioners from civil society and grassroots organisations, policymakers, social policy scientists, and economists. Wherever possible, the interviews were audio- or video-recorded and later transcribed to ensure accuracy and to allow for a detailed thematic analysis. These conversations illuminated not only the technical and administrative aspects of welfare delivery but also the socio-political and institutional dynamics that shape policy outcomes.

The insights gained from our primary research form the backbone of this report. They allowed us to go beyond generalised assessments and offer a grounded, first-hand account of the current landscape of UCTs in India. Our interviews also offered us a glimpse of the aspirations of different stakeholders when it comes to welfare.

The mixed methodology has enabled us to present a more comprehensive and informed analysis of both the potential and the limitations of cash transfer programmes in India. With this foundation we have proposed an agenda towards more sustainable welfare, to build resilient and self-reliant communities.

We invite you all to work on this mission with us, through identified pathways and newly emerging priority areas as the space further matures. Let's build a strong welfare fabric that enables inclusive and dignified development.

ABBREVIATIONS

BE

Budget Estimate

CCT

Conditional Cash Transfer

CRID

Citizen Resource Information Department

DBT

Direct Benefit Transfer

DCT

Direct Cash Transfer

DMEO

Development Monitoring and Evaluation Office

DPI

Digital Public Infrastructure

EBC

Economically Backward Classes

ESM

Ex-Servicemen

GDP

Gross Domestic Product

GSDP

Gross State Domestic Product

ID

Identification

IGNOAPS

Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme

IGNWPS

Indira Gandhi National Widow Pension Scheme

INR

Indian Rupees

KALIA

Krushak Assistance for Livelihood and Income Augmentation Scheme

KMUT

Kalaingar Magalir Urimai Thogai

KYC

Know Your Customer

LPG

Liquefied Petroleum/Propane Gas

MGNREGA

Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act

MMLBY

Mukhyamantri Majhi Ladaki Bahin Yojana

MPCE

Monthly Per Capita Expenditure

NSAP

National Social Assistance Programme

NTR

N.T. Rama Rao

PAHAL

Pratyaksh Hanstantrit Labh

PM

Prime Minister

PMJDY

Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana

PM KISAN

Pradhan Mantri Kisan Samman Nidhi Yojana

UBI

Universal Basic Income

UCT

Unconditional Cash Transfer

UDCW

Unpaid and Domestic Care Work

USA

United States of America

USD

United States Dollars

YSR

Y.S. Rajasekhara Reddy

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Project DEEP, 2025

Throughout history, societies have relied on structured support systems to protect their citizens from the harsh reality resulting from economic hardship and social discrimination.

As India races ahead on the pathway to become a five trillion-dollar economy by 2027, we must respond to the question on what is the role of the different stakeholders in ensuring that this growth is inclusive?

There is enough evidence from around the world that delivering money directly and unconditionally to citizens provides them the choice and purchasing power to shape their own lives and positive impact for communities.

It is a dignified and non-paternalistic approach that boosts the agency of those we seek to serve. It is also in line with welfare economics which suggests that when markets work well, allowing them free rein ensures that national resources are used most efficiently. However, if the free markets do well only economically, but do not result in equal opportunity and growth, or in basic needs being met for all citizens, then welfare-oriented governments should step in to redistribute wealth. This policy, like any other needs to be balanced on three pillars of evidence, fiscal prudence, and political salience.

FISCAL MANAGEMENT

The budget allocated to UCTs in the last decade has seen a remarkable 23x increase, outpacing the growth of the economy by ten times.

The total amount, INR 2,80,780 crore in 2024-25 (BE) translates to 0.9% of the GDP and 11% of the total social sector spending. This growth has also outpaced some of the country's flagship schemes, especially those that provide employment guarantee (MGNREGA) and food security (under NFSA), signaling a shift in the architecture of social protection. A large amount of INR 4.3 lakh crore in 2024-25 (BE)¹ continues to be allocated to subsidies, often with objectives overlapping with UCTs.

A preliminary analysis of the fiscal implications of this growth and a study from Axis Bank² reveals that the UCT budgets have not had a disproportionate impact on the liabilities of the country as % of GDP, and they have been primarily financed through expenditure-switching from other revenue spending. However, a more nuanced state-level analysis is required to understand the funding sources of their respective flagship schemes, and their implication on finances.

More importantly, as the trend of UCT adoption continues to rise, it is important to re-evaluate the welfare portfolio and allocation mechanisms.

- ◆ Traditional welfare measures, like subsidies, some of which are now regressive and ineffective can be examined for utility and impact, and phased out to make way for more modern tools of welfare.

- ◆ In-kind transfers that create a logistical burden on the exchequer without a proportionate impact in the citizens' lives, can be replaced with UCTs where appropriate to provide more choice, agency, and a boost to the local economy.
- ◆ Outcomes-based budgetary allocations can be linked to the Output Outcome Monitoring Framework³ being developed by the Development Monitoring and Evaluation Office (DMEO) at NITI Aayog for better resource allocation and impact accountability.

These will enable the states to adopt an approach to welfare reform that balances fiscal prudence, community impact, and market competitiveness.

ANALYSING DESIGN

Project DEEP has defined four key components: Frequency, Amount, Communication, and Timing (F.A.C.T.) through which the design of different UCT schemes can be analysed.

Currently, we see that women-centric schemes dominate, constituting 54% of the total budget allocation. The rest consists of schemes for farmers and other vulnerable populations like senior citizens, widows, and people with disabilities. There are however, several other groups whose intersectional vulnerabilities remain unaddressed. For example, while a street-dwelling woman may have access to women-oriented schemes, they do not meet her diverse and nuanced needs. The groups that are typically overlooked are street dwellers, transpeople, under-trial prisoners, gig workers and others for whom there is a huge data gap in the systems. About 10 crore individuals, including 2.3 crore adults, do not have Aadhaar cards, primarily constituting religious minorities, transpeople, scheduled tribes, and street dwellers.⁴

In order to ensure inclusive growth, there is a need to systematically identify multiple dimensions of citizen identities and their challenges, and design policies to address their vulnerabilities.

This also calls for portability of benefits, similar to 'One Nation, One Ration Card' so that those migrating for employment or other reasons are not excluded from receiving benefits.

In terms of frequency, monthly UCTs have steadily increased from 9 in 2015-16 to 32 in 2024-25, with 71% of the total budget being allocated to them. In the same duration, one-time transfers and those with other frequencies like PM KISAN, which provides benefits thrice a year, have been introduced, demonstrating a shift in the structure of UCTs, and an inclination to test newer models. Some governments have also introduced ex-gratia payments for pollution bans, fishing bans, heat waves, and other similar conditions. Formalising and mainstreaming automatic stabilisers, where additional support can be activated in an agile manner to specific areas and citizens in times of crisis or disaster, can be the next step of the evolution.

Assessing the adequacy of the benefits provided by UCT schemes leads to an interesting insight. The amount of money provided greatly varies: it can be anything from INR 2,400 to INR 2,00,000 on an annualised basis. While some monthly UCT schemes cover a paltry 2.7% of the monthly per capita expenditure (MPCE) in rural and urban areas, others provide benefits of upto 2x.* There is a need to critically examine whether schemes meet their intended objectives, and upgrade amounts accordingly.

Secondly, there is an opportunity to maximise the impact of cash-based policies by expanding the focus from consumption to investment to boost empowerment and self reliance in citizens.

This signifies a perspective shift from providing safety nets to enabling a trampoline effect that can lead to greater economic participation, and boost the overall growth of the country.

As the government forges ahead, relying on evidence to respond to challenges on nutrition, agency, and empowerment, civil society must play the role of conducting widespread pilots to build suitable models for different outcome areas and diverse demographic groups.

Philanthropy must provide patient, risk capital for such experiments that can guide intentional policy design for entire vulnerable populations.

Significant investments have been made to strengthen the infrastructure by which benefits are delivered but there is more to be done to simplify access and boost impact for citizens.

It is ideal to deliver funds with minimal demands on the citizens' time and bandwidth, and this ideal requires robust and updated databases. Several states have initiated the creation of Family IDs that can enable better scheme design, targeting, and delivery of benefits. In order to complement this, there is a need to strengthen the ecosystem within which citizens avail of schemes. Their financial access can be improved with more proximate application and withdrawal centres; better quality of service agents; requisite legal protection, and ease of redressal.

Civil society plays a key role in bridging the information asymmetry between citizens at the last mile and the government. They represent the voice of the underserved in policymaking conversations.

* Social security pensions in Punjab provide INR 200 per month which is 2.7% of the urban MPCE of INR 7383, whereas *NTR Bharosa Scheme* for people with disabilities in Andhra Pradesh provides INR 15,000 per month, which is 2x the rural and urban MPCE of INR 5,539 and INR 7,341, respectively.

UNDERSTANDING IMPACT

A key route to data-backed policymaking is through strong feedback loops enabled by continuous and rigorous evaluation of policies. Such exercises can bring to light the financial and non-financial impact of UCTs in a citizen's life; the multiplier effect in the economy; and its unintended consequences (both positive and negative). Knowing the drivers of decision-making, the changes in spending patterns, and its impact on the micro and macro indicators can aid policy design and outcome-based resource allocation, building a stronger bridge of trust and accountability between the state and citizens.

PERCEPTIONS

The overall perspective on UCTs ranges from optimistic to sceptical. Some experts consider it a critical tool for enhancing efficiency and impact, while others are doubtful of its political motives. But there is a consensus about its position in the welfare portfolio: UCTs are not a substitute for but complementary to essential state investments in health, education and so on.

To conclude, ensuring sustainable financial management, intentional design, and seamless implementation right up to the most remote and underserved locations is key to maximise the potential of cash-based policies, build improved lives for citizens, and substantially bridge inequity in the country. Different stakeholders play key roles to enable this movement.

WHAT DO WE MEAN BY UNCONDITIONAL CASH TRANSFERS?

Unconditional Cash Transfers (UCTs) have recently gained traction and they are often conflated with other welfare tools like Subsidies, Direct Cash Transfers (DCTs) and so on. In this report "UCTs" refers to any scheme where the recipient gets monetary benefits without needing to fulfil behavioural pre-conditions. These schemes maybe targeted or universal with regular or one-time payments - follow the map on the right to clarify these concepts by comparison.

EXAMPLES

PM KISAN is a *targeted, periodic and unconditional* transfer for farmers across the country.

The **National Family Benefit Scheme** is a *targeted, one-time, unconditional* transfer given to families living below the poverty line when they lose their breadwinners to death.

Universal Basic Income is an Unconditional Cash Transfer

Universal Basic Income (UBI) is a type of UCT because it provides periodic and *unconditional* cash payments to all individuals in an administrative unit without any means-testing or pre-conditions.

There are very few government schemes that meet this criteria. Those that come close is Iran's cash-based scheme for *all* its citizens to phase out for oil subsidies (2011), and Alaska's Permanent Fund Dividend (1982).

There are some UBI pilots in India that have been supported by philanthropic sources. They have been covered in Section 6.

SUBSIDIES are given to individuals or firms. They are meant to incentivise production or influence consumer behaviour by lowering costs of specific goods such as food, energy, transport or education.

DIRECT BENEFIT TRANSFERS (DBT) are linked to Aadhaar or other nationally verified IDs and directly provided to individuals. The benefits are of two types.

IN-KIND where recipients are provided goods and services for free or at a subsidised rate. This too can influence behaviour but **in-kind transfers** differ from subsidies as the government takes charge of procurement, movement, storage, and distribution. Food grains are the most popular example in this category.

In-kind transfers are usually made through an intermediary agency.

CASH (DCTS) includes schemes where financial benefits are directly transferred to the recipients' bank or postal accounts.

Direct Cash Transfers (DCTS) are versatile by design. The coverage, periodicity, and pre-conditions can be tailored to meet specific objectives or challenges in a region or a particular target group.

COVERAGE

PERIODICITY

CONDITIONALITY

UNIVERSAL where the benefits are given to everyone regardless of their social or economic status.

TARGETED where the benefits are given to specific sections of society who are deemed to be in need of financial assistance. For example, women, farmers, the elderly, and/or those marginalised by caste.

Means Testing is used to determine the recipient's eligibility based on observable household characteristics for an additional layer of targeting.

REGULAR cash transfers provide periodic economic and social security thereby reducing the pressure on low-income groups.

ONE-TIME cash transfers are typically provided as a lumpsum that can enable large purchases or investments in durable goods, pucca houses, land, jewellery and so on. One-time transfers are also given in calamitous circumstances.

CONDITIONAL cash transfers (CCTs) are provided before or after the recipients fulfil a behavioural requirement related to health, education or other welfare outcomes. For example, cash benefits may be provided to pregnant women at each trimester for adhering to their medical check-ups.

UNCONDITIONAL cash transfers (UCTs) have no such requirements. The recipients have greater agency to use the payments according to their needs, preferences, and aspirations.

01

RIGHTS-BASED

Unconditional cash transfers (UCTs) are often given for social security or poverty reduction to individuals, households or communities. They bypass the need for administrative intermediaries such as the local municipalities as the payments are directly transferred to the bank accounts of the intended recipients.

dignity.⁶ From a rights-based perspective, UCTs serve two functions. Firstly, they remove the need to prove one's merit or worthiness to access payments by making them condition-free. This lessens the risk of excluding individuals who struggle to fulfill pre-conditions. Importantly, unconditionality preserves an individual's right to financial autonomy as they can spend the money according to their needs and priorities. This signifies a paradigm shift in the power relations between the state and its people where the former is no longer a patronising figure or a benefactor. UCTs also serve as a remedy against the longstanding myth that poor people are not capable of managing their money without interference or guidance.⁷

NON-PATERNALISTIC

As this section shows, giving cash directly into the hands of people is the most instantaneous way of lessening their financial stress, and it arguably has the fastest outcomes as people allocate the money to fulfill their most urgent needs or obligations.

EFFICIENT

Poverty alleviation: Poverty alleviation and income stabilisation remain one of the key reasons for providing UCTs. Many middle and low income countries have cash transfer schemes for poor and economically vulnerable households. It is a widely successful tool for poverty alleviation because cash is fungible; it is not tethered to a specific need in the recipients' lives. Instead, they can use the money for immediate necessities and plan for future expenses. They can manage cash flows to prevent poverty-inducing situations down the line. It is the fastest and one of the most sustainable ways to eliminate poverty.

I think unconditional cash transfers have the potential to bypass the hierarchical process of the administrative system where beneficiaries are recipients of "benefits" and the delivery mechanism seems patronising. While this has not particularly caught on, I still stick to my support for it, that there's no conditionality which means you're not trying to dictate what people use the money for.

PROFESSOR MAITREESH GHATAK,
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Affirmation of fundamental rights: The purpose of UCTs is deeper than financial safety or welfare. It is an affirmation of people's right to access essential goods, services, and assets that affords them a decent standard of living and **protects their human**

Social justice: Additionally, UCTs are increasingly seen as a means to promote social justice.⁸ Marginalised groups such as indigenous communities or

marginalised castes often face systemic exclusion in education, employment, and income-generating opportunities. Meanwhile, farm workers, coal miners, and other informal workers who contribute to our economic systems through labour supply, taxes, and consumption receive insufficient or unstable pay while enduring tough working conditions with poor labour protection. UCTs can enhance the financial security of such marginalised groups, strengthening their bargaining power to advocate for better working conditions or to pursue new opportunities.

Unconditionality is also seen as a key element of climate justice where marginalised groups that are disproportionately affected by the unfolding crisis are offered reparations.

Economic productivity: Welfare instruments like consumer subsidies and in-kind transfers that are meant to provide financial security, stability or upliftment can worsen market failures when overused or poorly designed.^{9,10} For example, subsidising agricultural inputs like fertilisers can lead to over-consumption and subsequent pollution or soil degradation. As described above, UCTs have no such interference. The recipients can use the money at their discretion, to buy goods and services, save or invest.

They can generate economic productivity through multiplier effects as people have greater disposable income, which is often spent in local establishments enabling the circulation and growth of capital. Investments in long-term assets that yield

long-term returns benefit both the individual and the local economy in which they thrive.

Administrative efficiency:

Furthermore, in comparison to CCTs, in-kind payments, or subsidies, UCTs impose lesser burden on policymakers in terms of administration and enforcement. For example, there are logistical costs and effort attached to distributing food and perishable items that UCTs eliminate. This makes them more fiscally prudent but their end impact is also contingent on other factors like the availability of markets.

In conclusion, UCTs facilitate a more personal interaction between the government and its people, making it an attractive policy tool. However, they must be introduced with caution. If UCTs are merely chosen for administrative ease or to appeal to the public, they may get over-prioritised, at the expense of public investments in education, healthcare, transport and so on.

UCTs signify a paradigm shift away from the patronage model, and their adoption is likely to grow given their social, economic and political appeal.

In this report, we provide global and local examples to demonstrate the impact of UCTs on people's consumption patterns, food security, mental and physical health, well-being, education, and employment.

The existing scholarship on UCTs resoundingly indicates that providing cash, with no strings attached, improves people's lives.

HOW WAS DBT INTRODUCED IN LIEU OF THE LPG SUBSIDY IN INDIA?

India has significantly reformed its petroleum subsidy framework since 2010, adopting a "remove, target, and shift" strategy to reduce fiscal subsidies for fossil fuels.¹¹ The Direct Bank Transfer for Liquefied Petroleum and Gas Scheme (DBTL) was launched in 2013 to prevent subsidy leakages by transferring funds directly to consumers' bank accounts. However, an Aadhaar card was mandatory during the onboarding process leaving the households in low coverage areas disgruntled. In response, a year later, the government introduced the Pratyaksh Hanstantrit Labh (PAHAL), allowing LPG consumers to link their bank accounts without Aadhaar. The subsequent changes focussed on reaching economically-weaker groups.

Overall, PAHAL has led to the elimination of 4.15 cr duplicate, inactive, fake or non-existent LPG connections that in turn led to savings of INR 73,433 cr.¹²

Of the 2.45 cr non-subsidised customers, 1.13 cr have voluntarily relinquished their LPG subsidy under the Give It Up campaign.

UNDERSTANDING THE GLOBAL LANDSCAPE

DCT policies have been trialed in numerous countries across nearly every continent, each with varying objectives, designs, and outcomes. This diversity offers a valuable foundation of insights that can inform the Indian context.

Many DCTs in Africa are designed and targeted to support the most vulnerable individuals or households and are tied to specific conditions related to health, nutrition, education and so on. For instance, Morocco ran a 2-year DCT in five of the country's poorest regions with the objective of reducing high dropout rates of children from primary schools. Although the payments were allocated for a specific purpose, the conditions were not enforced. The scheme yielded positive results in reducing dropout rates by 7% in trial schools versus those that did not receive the payments.¹⁴

The outcomes of such quasi-UCT models can be useful to address market failures in India, across various sectors like education, and agriculture to name a few.

Furthermore, African cash transfer schemes have **evolved to integrate digital solutions** such as mobile banking services and electronic payments that almost eliminate the need to access physical service points thereby improving the efficiency of distribution especially in remote area where mobile-phone penetration is greater than access to banks or municipalities.^{15, 16}

However, many of the schemes in Africa, particularly in lower-income countries, rely substantially on external funding from international organisations or charities. This dependence causes ambiguity about the sustainability of such programmes. Hence, the financing models of these schemes limit their relevance to the Indian context.

Similarly, international organisations and developmental

aid programmes have been instrumental in financing DCT schemes in Haiti¹⁷, Columbia¹⁸, and Guatemala¹⁹ amongst other Central and South American countries. Cash transfer programmes have been part of the policy discourse in this region since the early 1990s, and you can find programmes in almost every country, but many of them are launched in response to natural disasters, humanitarian crises, or severe economic recessions.

In terms of government-led schemes, *Bolsa Família* in Brazil remains a prominent example from the region. It aims to reduce severe poverty and improve educational and health outcomes for children. Apart from its intended objectives, the scheme has been instrumental in integrating millions of people into the economic and social mainstream of the country.²⁰

From 1997 to 2019, Mexico's national CCT program—Oportunidades (formerly Progresá, later Prospera)—provided support for healthcare, education, and nutrition to over 26 million people. **Though eventually discontinued, it remains one of the largest and longest-running DCT programs globally.**²¹ Both schemes serve as useful case studies for India due to their scale, covering millions of residents, for years.

Iran's unconditional and universal cash transfer scheme is widely studied. It remains one of the few case studies of a long-term and national scheme in Asia. However, the scheme has gradually lost public appeal in Iran largely due to inflationary pressures in the country following global economic sanctions. Increasingly-universal distributions led to criticism that the government had lost focus of the scheme's original objectives, and that the universality was aggravating inflation.²²

Iran, and to that effect, Indonesia²³ are interesting cases for India since both countries used UCTs to replace energy and fuel subsidies.

Fluctuations in public support for cash transfer schemes provide an important lesson for India which has a large tax-paying middle class population. Government-led cash transfer schemes have also been implemented in countries neighbouring India such as Pakistan and Nepal as well as Indonesia, South Korea, and Turkey.

Over the past two decades, numerous UCT initiatives, particularly basic income schemes, have been launched across Europe by policymakers, researchers, and civil society organisations. However, with the slight exception of Spain,²⁴ scaling up UBI remains a critical challenge, partly because most European countries already have a myriad of means-tested and conditional social-protection schemes. This limits the public

and political support for an unconditional income. As a result, many of the pilot studies are primarily meant to evaluate the feasibility and the benefits of basic income. Their scope is limited to a small segment of the population and they run only for a fixed duration.

On the other hand, basic income pilots in the USA offer valuable lessons for India because their regional implementation parallels India's cash transfer schemes at the state level, in scale. Second, the USA focuses on gender-disaggregated impacts that can inform India's women-centric transfer schemes. They excel at data collection and evaluation whereas India's efforts largely focus on eligibility and payment delivery. India can refine its monitoring, evaluation, and policy design by meaningfully learning from the USA.

UCTs & SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

UCTs align well with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) issued by the United Nations in 2015 to which India is a signatory.¹³

UCTs address the fundamental cause of poverty: lack of cash. They give people the financial agency to address their immediate needs and possibly contribute towards the future.

UCTs can have multifaceted benefits for gender equality. In India, various states have launched UCTs for women, providing them with greater spending power and economic autonomy; encouraging employment or entrepreneurship; and increasing opportunities for education and nutrition.

Periodic UCTs, a commonly deployed tool, result in consumption smoothening and ensure food security.

The popular rhetoric that UCTs disincentivise employment ignores the problems of today's labour markets such as unequal access to jobs; underpaid or precarious work; unfair contracts to name a few. Several trials have demonstrated that UCTs can empower people to seek secure and fair employment, engage in professional development opportunities, or set up their own enterprises.

Targeted UCTs such as the Matru Vandana Yojana in India are being deployed to improve health and nutrition for pregnant women as well as new-borns and young children.

Several UCTs and CCTs around the world, like *Bolsa Familia* in Brazil have shown significant improvements in enrolment and retention of children in schools, especially for girls.

UCTs can reach historically neglected communities with means testing. The amount and the frequency of the benefits can also be designed to help them build assets that are otherwise beyond their means.

02

Currently, the provision of social services in India spans many key areas including poverty alleviation; sports, art and culture; public health; nutrition; education; family welfare; water supply and sanitation; housing and urban development; welfare initiatives for Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, and Other Backward Classes; labour welfare; social security; and relief for natural disasters.

By this definition, the total expenditure on social services by the Union and State Governments has grown from INR 10.4 lakh crore to INR 25.7 lakh crore between 2016-17 and 2024-25 (BE) *

In their analysis, Maitreesh Ghatak and Karthik Muralidharan (2019)²⁵ contextualise unconditional cash transfers (UCTs) as part of India's anti-poverty strategy. They highlight its potential to:

i) Reduce poverty through direct income support or an Inclusive Growth Dividend +

ii) Improve financial access and economic security by providing households with a predictable income stream.

iii) Foster systemic efficiency in social welfare by creating an attainable benchmark to evaluate public expenditures.

Importantly, they contend that an Inclusive Growth Dividend would not replace existing welfare

programmes immediately but would provide an additional tool to alleviate poverty while mitigating concerns regarding a universal basic income (UBI).

Their analysis resonates with the **emerging policy preference** for more direct forms of welfare provision. Health, education and rural development have been traditionally prioritised by the government. Within this, there has been a clear increase in budget allocations for schemes that provide direct entitlements such as housing (Pradhan Mantri Awaas Yojana - Gramin), sanitation (Swachh Bharat Mission - Grameen), maternal health (PM Matru Vandana Yojana) and investment support (PM Kisan Samman Nidhi Yojana or PM KISAN).

UCTs as a form of direct benefits are not new in India. The Samajik Suraksha Vridhavastha Pension Scheme and the Raksha Mantri Ex-Servicemen Welfare Fund were introduced in 1981 making them the earliest examples of UCTs in the country. But the prominence of such schemes as a key policy promise began to grow at the turn of the 21st century.

HOW HAS THE MOVEMENT TOWARDS UNCONDITIONAL CASH TRANSFERS EVOLVED IN INDIA?

The rise of UCTs can be divided into three phases starting from the mid-2000s.

See page 24 for more.

* (BE) indicates Budget Estimate for the year 2024-25 when the budgets were announced at the national and state levels. This is applicable for the whole report though we have not repeated the abbreviation for better readability.

+ Inclusive Growth Dividend is a policy idea in India that suggests transferring a fixed percentage of GDP per capita to every citizen to promote equitable distribution of wealth and opportunities.

A TALE OF TWO NATIONS: REJECTED IN SWITZERLAND, PROPOSED IN INDIA!

In 2016, Switzerland held a referendum on introducing universal basic income (UBI) for all its citizens that was decisively rejected with 76.9% votes against it.²⁹ The proposed scheme aimed to provide a guaranteed income, funded by taxes and reallocated social security payments. It did not gain favour because it was considered potentially disruptive to the country's economic and social system. The existing welfare structures already ensured dignity, and there was some concern that UBI would discourage workforce participation while adding to the annual financial burden.

Around the same time, one of the Members of Parliament from Sultanpur, became the first Indian politician to advocate for UBI, presenting the idea as an opinion piece in *The Hindu*.³⁰ The article argued that regular cash payments could improve financial security, reduce poverty, and offer a more stable social safety net. It referenced international experiments such as Canada's "Mincome" trial, which showed that predictable income support enhanced health and education outcomes. The article also highlighted India's pilot programmes including an experiment in Madhya Pradesh that led to improved household sanitation, nutrition, and financial inclusion. While acknowledging challenges in implementation, it advocated for a gradual rollout of basic income schemes, backed by extensive data and pilot studies, to ensure effectiveness. His vision emphasised autonomy, economic empowerment, and sustainable development, positioning UBI as a transformative step toward a more equitable future for India.

EVOLUTION OF UNCONDITIONAL CASH TRANSFERS IN INDIA

2007 - 2017

The adoption of DCTs was driven in part by a growing concern for administrative efficiency. For instance, the then Chief Economic Advisor of India, Arvind Subramanian proposed that the central government should replace food, fuel, and fertiliser subsidies with a single DCT scheme to reduce the administrative burden on the public welfare systems in his paper titled 'The Case for DCTs to the Poor.'²⁶

This period also saw a series of institutional and technological reforms that laid the groundwork for more effective implementation of DCTs. These included the introduction of Aadhaar in 2009; the DBT mission in 2013; and the opening of zero balance accounts at scale under Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) from 2014.

The large-scale enrolment of individuals under the Aadhaar system facilitated the DBT mission across India. The first phase was especially impactful in bringing rural and semi-urban populations as well as women into formal finance. The DBT mission was launched to enhance transparency and minimise leakage in the welfare protection system by directly transferring in-kind or cash benefits to recipients.

In the absence of direct cash transfers, you would think everyone has received the benefit. One indicator to check this is that spending across all centrally-sponsored and central schemes was 100%. Now there is much more transparency, where you can trace the recipient and identify exclusions and actual outlay.

PROFESSOR N.R. BHANUMURTHY, DIRECTOR,
MADRAS SCHOOL OF ECONOMICS

ADMINISTRATIVE EFFICIENCY

2018 - 2019

The second phase emerged in response to India's deepening agrarian crisis between 2018 and 2019 that saw thousands of farmers rallying across the country for better financial security.

Past loan waivers by governments had proven ineffective simultaneously ruining farmers' credit and weakening the banking system.

The farming community was terribly affected the demonetisation in 2016 because it depended on the liquidity of cash for its day-to-day transactions. While official figures are not available, according to data released by the National Crime Record Bureau, 10,655 people working in agriculture died by suicide in 2017.³¹

It is around this time that the Telangana government launched *Rythu Bandhu* (Farmer's Investment Support Scheme), which entailed an unconditional cash transfer of INR 10,000 per year to each farmer timed to two crop cycles. The scheme was successful in its intended objective of providing investment support to farmers, and it has been replicated in several states including Odisha and West Bengal. PM KISAN at the Central level was also modelled on *Rythu Bandhu*. It provides INR 6,000 annually to all farmers and reaches half of the country's population.

Rythu Bandhu deviates from the classical sense of basic income because it ties assistance to the ownership of land rather than the farmer's circumstances. But what it did establish, undeniably, was the principle of unconditional transfers. And that they can have very positive consequences in terms of growth in agricultural production. This success, both economic and electoral, led the political parties to introduce unconditional transfers to women. This shift in political thinking—moving away from subsidies to direct cash—is irreversible.

DR SARATH DAVALA, PRESIDENT, BASIC INCOME
EARTH NETWORK; CO-DIRECTOR, WORKFREE

AGRARIAN CRISIS

138 CRORE PEOPLE

were enrolled within the Aadhaar system by October 2024.²⁷

55 CRORE ACCOUNTS

have been opened under the Jan Dhan Yojana with a cumulative deposit of roughly INR 2.5 lakh cr as of 2025. This is an over 15-fold increase since the scheme's launch.²⁸

37.29 CRORE RUPAY CARDS*

have been issued to PMJDY account holders as of 2025.²⁸

* RuPay is an affordable payment solution for Indian consumers by the National Payments Corporation of India. It offers a wide range of services like debit and credit cards, and electronic payments.

2019 ONWARDS

In this phase DCT schemes were increasingly centred on women's economic welfare and autonomy. Though they were initially introduced to support household incomes after the COVID-19 pandemic, now women-oriented schemes are an integral part of social protection in 14 states. They provide a monthly income support of INR 1,000 to INR 2,500 for low-income households.

In a different yet related context, the discourse on compensating unpaid domestic labour gained attention in the run up to the 2021 Tamil Nadu Assembly Elections and more broadly, the recognition of women as entrepreneurs and active economic participants has motivated new DCT schemes in some states.

See Page 26 where we've put the spotlight on the debate on cash transfers as compensation for unpaid work.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, UCTs have continually featured in India's welfare provisions. However, the objectives to implement them have evolved from administrative efficiency approach to financial safety in times of crisis. With time, the targeting has also expanded from small groups like ex-servicemen or pensioners to broader categories. This trend corresponds with the increasing acceptance of unconditionality and universality within sub-populations who are considered to be socio-economically vulnerable such as women and farmers.

RECOGNITION OF WOMEN IN THE SOCIAL AND POLITICAL ECONOMY

The political party *Makkal Needhi Maiam* in Tamil Nadu, led by veteran actor Kamal Haasan promised assured payment to women who are full-time homemakers,³² at the polls in 2021. The payment was meant to compensate for their previously undervalued and unpaid labour at home.³³ Advocates argue that such recognition would provide financial independence to homemakers, elevating their status and reducing their dependence on male earners.³³ It could empower women by acknowledging their contributions, providing financial autonomy, and encouraging more gender-sensitive policies.

Conversely, the policy could unintentionally reinforce traditional gender roles by discouraging women to participate in the formal workforce, and increasing social isolation. Funding sustainability and defining eligibility criteria also pose significant challenges.

A more balanced approach could involve universal cash transfers, shared domestic responsibilities, and increased investment in childcare services to alleviate household burdens while enabling women to pursue economic opportunities beyond the home.

ECOSYSTEM OF DELIVERING CASH TRANSFERS IN INDIA

The process of delivering cash transfers has been broken down into four stages ranging from identifying funds, building schemes, implementing and then evaluating their impact. While the government remains the operator at scale, here are a few other stakeholders in the ecosystem.

	NON-PROFITS & PRIVATE INSTITUTES	ACADEMICS	PHILANTHROPY	
FISCAL MANAGEMENT	Identify areas of revenue augmentation and cost reduction, and incorporate schemes within fiscal boundaries	Indus Action ³⁴ is working with various states to unlock the unutilised cess within the Building and Other Construction Workers Act to provide a basic income to construction workers.	Multiple economists have calculated different permutations for basic income in India. ^{38,25}	
DESIGN	Create programmes based on local needs and global evidence with details on target audience, frequency, and amount of transfer and communication	Project DEEP ³⁵ implements programmes in vulnerable communities to understand their spending patterns and create frameworks for innovative, contextual, and effective design.	Kartik Muralidharan and Maitreesh Ghatak's paper on Inclusive Growth Dividend ²⁵ provides a detailed design and implementation roadmap for UBI in India.	UNICEF funded the first ever pilot on basic income in India making it a cornerstone of the movement. ⁴⁰
IMPLEMENTATION	Identify and solve gaps in last mile delivery by addressing inclusion and exclusion errors, and building channels for grievance redressal	Samagra ³⁶ works with selected states to build a robust family database that ensures proactive welfare delivery from cradle to grave and reduces targeting errors.	Same as above	The Gates Foundation has invested in improving the digital architecture and agricultural credit system that is the backbone of implementation. ⁴¹
EVALUATION	To evaluate intended and unintended impact across intersections and to build feedback loops with citizens	Pratichi Trust ³⁷ has collaborated with the West Bengal government to analyse the impact of the <i>Lakshmir Bhandar Scheme</i> . This includes outcomes that saw positive, limited, or no change.		WorkFREE ³⁹ have been studying how basic income can provide freedom of choice in the labour market to inform scaled pro-poor social protection reform.

Additionally, the **Indian Basic Income Coalition (iBIC)**⁴² was launched in March 2023 by Indus Action, the India Network for Basic Income, Project DEEP, and WorkFREE to build a more dignified, and future-ready social policy framework for India. There is clear scope to foster more of these collaborations to ensure our approach to cash transfers is truly multidisciplinary and robust.

03

India's economy grew almost 2.3 times in the last decade from INR 137 lakh crore in 2015-16 to INR 324 lakh crore in 2024-25 despite global turmoils like the COVID-19 pandemic. The expenditure on social services similarly grew from INR 10.41 lakh crore in 2016-17 to INR 25.67 lakh crore in 2024-25.

Crucially, total budget allocated to UCTs increased by a remarkable 23-fold in the time period under discussion.

The total budgetary allocation for UCTs by the Union and State Governments increased from INR 12,188 crore in 2015-16 to INR 2,80,780.5 crore in 2024-25.

This suggests that UCTs are an increasingly important feature of India's overall welfare strategy.

THE BUDGET ALLOCATION FOR UCT SCHEMES IS AT 0.9% OF THE GDP

Source: Budget documents of the Union and State Governments (various years); Economic Survey 2024-25, Ministry of Finance⁴³

See Annexure 2

UCT SCHEMES MAKE UP 11% OF THE TOTAL SOCIAL SECTOR SPENDING

Source: Budget documents of the Union and State Governments (various years); Economic Survey 2024-25, Ministry of Finance⁴³

See Annexure 2

There was an uptick in the budgetary allocation to UCTs in 2019 due to the launch of various schemes for farmers. See Section 2 for more information on the Evolution of UCTs in India.

DID YOU KNOW

India's expenditure on UCTs was a whopping INR 2,80,780.5 crore or USD 32.71 billion in 2024-25. * This outpaces the entire nominal GDP of countries like Iceland, Senegal, and Georgia.⁴⁴

In other words, India invests more in UCTs than what these nations generate in a year!

* Based on the 2024-25 exchange rate, USD1 = INR 85.832

Interestingly, the share of spending by the Centre and states has reversed, where 70% of the allocation was through the the former in 2015-16 but it reduced to 25% in 2024-25. This highlights the **dominant role of state governments in funding and implementing UCTs**.

The central share of spending on UCTs rose abruptly in 2020-2021 by ~79% due to a significant allocation of INR 30,000 crore to women account holders during the COVID-19 pandemic.

CENTRE vs STATES' BUDGETARY ALLOCATION FOR UCTs

Source: Budget documents of the Union and State Governments (various years); Economic Survey 2024-25, Ministry of Finance ⁴³

SOMETIMES, UCT ALLOCATIONS DRIVE BUDGETARY SPENDS

A whopping 9% of Maharashtra's total revenue expenditure is dedicated to the *Mukhyamantri Majhi Ladaki Bahin Yojana*.⁴⁵

Also, the total amount allocated for this scheme is greater than the entire budget of its implementing department.

At the Central level, close to half of the expenditure for the Department of Agriculture and Farmers' Welfare has been allocated to PM KISAN at INR 60,000 crore 2024-25.

EXPENDITURE ON FOOD SUBSIDIES, MGNREGA & UCT SCHEMES

Disclaimer: Since the Union Government accounts for the majority of spending on MGNREGA and food subsidies compared to the states and UTs, only the former's expenditure has been considered.

Source: Budget documents of the Union and State Governments (various years); Economic Survey 2024-25, Ministry of Finance⁴³

See Annexure 2

KEY

FOOD SUBSIDY SPENDING BY THE CENTRE

TOTAL SPENDING ON UCT SCHEMES BY THE CENTRE AND STATES

MGNREGA SPENDING BY THE CENTRE

The trend for financing UCTs has grown at a faster pace than some of India's most popular social welfare programmes.

Rural employment guarantee and food security have been key focus areas for the government for many years. For example, the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act 2005 (MGNREGA) was a flagship initiative of the government to enhance the livelihood security of people in rural areas by providing guaranteed employment for 100 days.

Alongside, the National Food Security Act 2013 continues to entitle vulnerable people to receive subsidised food grains through a targeted public distribution system. During the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic, the share of food subsidies amongst the total amount of subsidies offered by the Union Government reached a peak of 71.4%, reflecting heightened policy focus. However, in recent years, the budgetary growth of UCTs has outpaced both schemes, signalling a shift in the architecture of social protection.

We have given [the government] a matrix on phasing out food subsidies with cash transfers in three phases. Those states with better banking infrastructure, women's literacy, and roads should move to it in the 1st phase. While others that rely on food imports and have poorer connectivity, like the Northeast, should do it in the last stage.

SIRAJ HUSSAIN, UNION SECRETARY, MINISTRY OF FOOD PROCESSING (2013-2015); ADVISOR, FEDERATION OF INDIAN CHAMBERS OF COMMERCE AND INDUSTRY

ANALYSING THE FISCAL BURDEN

UCT allocations, total liabilities and outstanding liabilities

KEY

- TOTAL OUTSTANDING LIABILITIES OF CENTRE & STATES
- COMBINED TOTAL LIABILITIES OF CENTRE & STATES
- OVER ALL SPENDING ON UCT SCHEMES BY CENTRE & STATES

Source: Budget documents of the Union and State Governments (various years); Handbook of Statistics on Indian States 2024, Reserve Bank of India.⁴⁶

See Annexure 2

When analysed as % of GDP, the liabilities and outstanding liabilities at an aggregate level, have remained largely constant, in the mid-80's range. This is indicative that the rise in UCTs is linked to the overall economic growth of the country and is **not causing a disproportionate increase in the liability burden.**

Based on preliminary observations, we see that the launch of major UCTs in various states also coincides with an uptick of varied degrees in the liabilities. However, consolidation efforts seem to be undertaken as reflected in the downward trend in subsequent years. For example, the launch of various schemes including *YSR Rythu Bharosa* in Andhra Pradesh across 2019 and 2020 saw a rise in the state's total outstanding liabilities by 2.9% of the GSDP. However, this has subsequently come down again and settled at a

pre-scheme introduction level of ~34% of GSDP. Similar trends of an uptick with a subsequent calibration are observed in 2021 for Madhya Pradesh with the *Ladli Behen Scheme* and West Bengal with *Lakshmir Bhandar*.⁴⁷

It is important to note that Andhra Pradesh has exhibited fluctuating outstanding liability levels, and West Bengal has consistently maintained a higher debt-to-GSDP ratio, reflecting substantial fiscal commitments and borrowing trends.

A potential reason is highlighted in a recent Axis Bank report² which highlights that UCT schemes are primarily financed through expenditure-switching from other revenue spending, with only some states relying on increased fiscal deficits. While a detailed analysis is beyond the scope of this report, there is significant value in

examining the funding source of these large ticket schemes across different state governments, and what impact it has had on overall state finances.

That has been the political economy of India. It has been an extraordinarily strong point that the Indian political system doesn't go bankrupt despite multiple freebies as do so many of our neighbours. Perhaps a slightly larger share of freebies is becoming cash, but all I can say is that the system is functioning so far, and I have no reason to think it's going to go downhill, so we will manage.

SWAMINATHAN AIYER, ECONOMIST,
JOURNALIST; CONSULTING EDITOR,
ECONOMIC TIMES

There has been a rise in UCTs as the preferred mode of social and economic development with INR 2,80,780 crore being allocated to these schemes in 2024-25. That is 0.9% of the GDP and 11% of the total social sector spending. This calls for governments to optimise the efficiency and quality of their expenditure to ensure UCTs truly serve the people.

In India, different departments launch different welfare schemes to address a specific challenge or outcome. They may introduce subsidies; build social infrastructure, and state capacities; and/or provide social protection schemes. In the last decade, significant investments were also made to enhance welfare delivery with technology and last-mile citizen identification. This formed the backbone of cash-based policies in India. The JAM trinity (Jan Dhan bank accounts, Aadhaar, and mobile penetration) with the DBT Mission created a strong foundation for benefits to be directly transferred to identified citizens in need.

However, this advancement in processes has not been accompanied by the systematic removal of redundancies. Traditional tools of welfare that are no longer effective or do not serve their original purposes continue to co-exist with new ones, creating a fiscal and administrative burden on the state. For example, farmers continue to receive various fertiliser and seed subsidies even after the introduction of direct cash transfers. Of the total ~INR 4.3 lakh cr⁴⁸ allocated by the Union to subsidies in 2025-26, ~INR 1.7 lakh cr is towards fertilisers.

Given that both, UCTs and subsidies, are meant to improve agricultural productivity, there is merit in exploring if these measures can be consolidated.

Additionally, the number of schemes at the state level are rising every year. For example, in Maharashtra alone, there are over 2,000 schemes.⁴⁹ This growing number without rationalisation leads to a tokenistic allocation of funds, impeding the achievement of outcomes.

There are three potential pathways to address these challenges:

01

All subsidies can be analysed in terms of necessity, efficiency, and unintended consequences. Those faring poorly can be gradually phased out and replaced with better alternatives including UCTs. This gives people greater freedom to choose their supplier, goods, and services. The fiscal pressure does not fall on a handful of suppliers, and the quality of supply is likely to improve with **increased bargaining power** on the part of consumers. It also addresses the issue of misuse and wastage given that no particular product is incentivised.

02

The outcomes of in-kind transfers and token schemes can be evaluated and those that do not meet their objectives or overlap with the potential outcomes of a UCT can be replaced appropriately. Providing money instead of goods

greatly **boosts the circulation of capital in the local economy**, enabling the growth of small enterprises. It also ensures choice and prioritisation for the customer.

03

Outcome-based budget allocations can be introduced to build more accountability in the system. They have worked effectively in philanthropy and civil society, and can be adopted for financial management in the government too. The Development Monitoring and Evaluation Office (DMEO) at NITI Aayog has been working on an Output Outcome Monitoring Framework (OOMF) to shift from simply measuring physical and financial progress to a governance model based on outcomes. This can be adopted by all states, and it can become the basis for **performance-based budgeting** to improve decision-making, resource allocation, accountability, and impact.

Reviewing welfare to remove redundancies will make more fiscal space for other approaches including UCTs. However, for the latter to be successful, they may need to be inflation indexed and they require the existence of a free and fair market in the proximity.

We must also caution against a narrow view of UCTs that only considers economic efficiency. There is merit in adopting a balanced outlook that puts equal emphasis on fiscal prudence, community impact, and market competitiveness.

04

TARGETING MECHANISMS

India currently does not have cash-based policies that are implemented universally i.e. for the entire population. However, targeting strategies have advanced, incorporating diverse mechanisms, and policies have broadened to cover a larger segment of vulnerable populations.

Geographic targeting is where resources are directed to districts or blocks exhibiting the highest levels of poverty and inequality and in **demographic targeting** groups are chosen based on social factors like gender or age, and vulnerability factors like disability.

Proxy means testing is used when direct income data is unreliable, unavailable, or difficult to verify, relying instead on observable household characteristics to estimate economic status and ensure more accurate targeting of social assistance. In addition, **community-based targeting** relies on local communities to participate in the selection and validation of individuals eligible for benefits.

While geographic targeting enables higher efficiency, the rest emphasise equity. However, there are logistical challenges associated with means testing that is used for equitable targeting because the documentation levels are poor for many vulnerable people who are typically engaged in informal work, or otherwise excluded from formal labour and financial markets.

Demographic targeting is used to provide cash transfers to a specific segment of the population that

is at increased risk of poverty or economic insecurity. Currently, a large number of UCT schemes are directed towards specific demographics, with some additional characteristics of exclusions being introduced to sharpen the focus.

While some are universal within a defined group, many others have means testing even within an identified group. Though universality remains debated, we are seeing a trend towards exclusion criteria, reducing to some extent the burden of eligibility proof on the recipient.

Within demographic targeting, women-focussed schemes are most popular, making up 54% of the total budget allocated to unconditional cash transfers.

Though India has had pension schemes for over three decades to support the elderly, widows, people with disabilities and others, their share in the total budget is lower.

THE TOTAL NUMBER OF UNCONDITIONAL CASH TRANSFER SCHEMES AND THEIR BUDGETARY ALLOCATION IN 2024-25 ON THE BASIS OF TARGET GROUPS

WOMEN

Number of schemes	Budgetary allocation
14	INR 1,51,071

53.8%

FARMERS

Number of schemes	Budgetary allocation
4	INR 69,435

24.7%

VULNERABILITY-BASED

Number of schemes	Budgetary allocation
22	INR 60,249

21.5%

LIVELIHOOD-BASED

Number of schemes	Budgetary allocation
1	INR 25

0.0%

Total budgetary allocation for UCT schemes
INR 2,80,780

Source: Budget documents of the Union and State Governments in 2025-25 (BE). This graphic has been constructed on the basis of 41 UCT schemes for which budgetary allocation data is available for 2024-25 (BE). Project DEEP has hitherto identified 71 UCTs.
See Annexure 1A

ALL THE BUDGET FIGURES ARE IN CRORE

Project DEEP has defined four key components, Frequency, Amount, Communication, and Timing (FACT) to analyse UCTs in terms of their scheme design.

THE IMPACT OF FREQUENCY AND TIMING OF PAYMENTS

The frequency at which the benefits of the scheme are disbursed greatly influences its effectiveness.

Currently in India, **monthly transfers** are most preferred because of their positive impact on the community, and the way in which the cash flows can be phased, for the state finances. The majority of vulnerability-based and women-focused UCTs follow this model, providing a predictable source of support for the recipients that enables improved consumption, and relief from rising prices due to inflation. For example, the *Gruhalaxmi Scheme* in Karnataka provides INR 2,000 to women who head their households. Monthly transfers also provide a security cover to those who may have minimal or no avenues of earnings.

Less frequent disbursements, such as **annual** or **one-time payments**, cater to specific needs like livelihood disruptions or major life events (when the main earning member of the family dies), while **milestone-based transfers** align with agricultural cycles and investment requirements. For example, Odisha provides INR 15,000 in one installment to all the families that are adversely-affected

by a fishing ban that lasts for six months of the year.

When the benefits are spread across the year, they enable consumption smoothening and behaviour change but the amount per instalment is likely to be lower. On the other hand, larger amounts at lower frequencies can lead to strategic investments and resilience if they are aligned with specific occurrences in the recipients' lives.

The landscape of UCTs has undergone a significant transformation between 2015-16 and 2024-25, both in terms of periodicity and budget allocation.

Despite the increase in monthly transfers from nine in 2015-16 to 32 in 2024-25, their share in the total budgetary allocation has declined from 94.8% to 70.97%, indicating a diversification in scheme design.

Annual and one-time UCTs that were either non-existent or minimally represented in 2015-16, have gained prominence. For example, the National Family Benefit Scheme (NFBS) under the National Social Assistance Programme (NSAP) offers a one-time lumpsum of INR 20,000 to families below the poverty line when they lose their breadwinner, to relieve some of their hardships.⁵¹

The introduction of the "Other" category, covering four UCTs, also marks a major shift. It gets INR 69,435 crore or 24.73% of the total allocation, and includes schemes that provide periodic instalments like PM KISAN where farmers receive benefits thrice a year.

ODISHA'S TARGETING MECHANISM FOR KALIA

The Krushak Assistance for Livelihood and Income Augmentation Scheme (KALIA), launched by the Odisha government in December 2018, aims to accelerate agricultural prosperity and reduce poverty.⁵⁰

It is the only farmer-centric scheme that provides support for cultivators and farmers without land. The benefits are varied based on vulnerability.

Those owning land receive INR 5,000 per farm family per season for small and marginal farmers to cover initial investments, amounting to INR 10,000 annually, whereas landless agricultural households receive INR 12,500 per household. Additionally INR 10,000 per family is provided to households unable to engage in cultivation or livelihood activities due to age, disability, or illness.

Odisha used various datasets like the Agriculture Census 2015-16, the National Social Assistance Programme, 70th Round Situation Assessment Survey of Agricultural Households (2012-13), and the Socio-Economic Caste Census to identify landless farmers for KALIA. The field verification was done through gram panchayats, and transparency measures were enabled through self-declared applications and cross-referencing of DBT databases with existing welfare programmes.

This multi-layered approach, along with a staggered roll out of the scheme minimised exclusion errors while ensuring the scheme reached the most vulnerable.

Analysing UCT schemes based on their frequency and budgetary allocation

Source: Budget documents of the Union and State Governments in 2025-25 (BE). This chart has been constructed on the basis of 41 UCT schemes for which budgetary allocation data is available for 2024-25 (BE). Project DEEP has hitherto identified 71 UCTs

See Annexure 1A

DETERMINING THE APPROPRIATE AMOUNTS FOR DISTRIBUTION

The total amount provided to recipients depends on the scheme's objectives, fiscal considerations and feasibility. There can be a **fixed universal amount** for the whole target group, **variable amounts** based on vulnerabilities, or a **graduated structure** based on milestones. A fixed universal

amount is easiest to administer. For example, the *Shravanbal Seva State Pension Scheme* of Maharashtra provides monthly assistance of INR 600 to all destitute senior citizens.⁵²

The *NT Rama Rao Bharosa Pension Scheme (NTR)* in Andhra Pradesh, on the other hand, has a **multi-tiered or graded structure**, based on the degree of vulnerability. It provides INR 4,000 per month to the elderly, widows, single women, weavers, toddy tappers, fishermen, transgender individuals, traditional cobblers, those availing of Antiretroviral Therapy for HIV, and *dappu* artists. * People with disabilities, and multiple deformities due to leprosy receive INR 6,000 per month.⁵³ Individuals suffering from complete

impairment, chronic diseases or chronic kidney disease receive a much higher UCT of INR 15,000 and INR 10,000 per month respectively.

Some schemes like *Rythu Bandhu* in Telangana provide **tiered benefits** based on landholding, and they are economically sound (more acres, more benefit), but they fall short in terms of equity because richer farmers benefit more than those in need.

* *Dappu* artists are primarily members of the Madiga community, a Scheduled Caste (SC) in Telangana and Andhra Pradesh, who make and play the *dappu*, a percussion instrument that has cultural and religious significance in the region.

Frequency distribution of yearly amounts transferred

Source: Budget documents of Union and State Governments; myScheme (Government of India's website)

Are the benefits provided by UCT schemes sufficient to meet people's consumption needs?

There are 17 schemes that provide INR 1,000 a month to different demographics. However, across the spectrum, individuals can receive anything from an annual cash flow of INR 2,400 (for example, Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme for 60-79 years) to INR 1,80,000 (*NTR Bharosa* in Andhra Pradesh for those who are completely disabled) in monthly transfers. Meanwhile, schemes like *Krishak Bondhu* in West Bengal provide a one-time benefit of INR 2,00,000 upon the demise of a farmer or a registered *bhagchasi* (sharecropper) (aged 18-60 years) to their legal heirs.

With the varied range of amounts being provided across schemes, it is interesting to note how they impact a family's spending choices and patterns.

Given that a larger concentration of schemes provide monthly benefits meant for improvements in consumption, we have analysed how the amount provided compares to the monthly per capita expenditure in different states. See the next page for more.

COMPARING THE BENEFITS PROVIDED BY VARIOUS UCT SCHEMES TO THE URBAN MPCE*

See Annexure 4

The MPCE in urban areas, across states, ranges between INR 5,114 to INR 13,425.

* Monthly Per Capita Expenditure

COMPARING THE BENEFITS PROVIDED BY VARIOUS UCT SCHEMES TO THE RURAL MPCE *

See Annexure 4

The MPCE in rural areas, across states, ranges between INR 2,927 and INR 8,857.

The MPCE in rural areas across different states ranges from INR 2,927 to INR 8,857, while the same in urban areas is INR 5,114 to INR 13,425. Comparing these to the benefits provided by monthly UCTs led to 3 key findings:

01

Andhra Pradesh and Haryana pay higher pensions than other states and the Centre. Many of Haryana's pension schemes (such as the Old Age Samman Allowance Scheme, Financial Assistance to Destitute Women and Widows, and Pension to Differently Aabled Person) provide INR 2,500 or more per month, which is almost half of the MPCE in rural areas and one-third in urban areas, indicating significant social protection.

The monthly amount transferred under the *NTR Bharosa Pension Scheme* to completely disabled individuals in Andhra Pradesh is the highest at INR 15,000 per month, totalling to INR 1,80,000 of annual benefits per person. It accounts for 270.81% of rural MPCE and 204.33% of urban MPCE (at the state level) in 2023-24.

On the other hand, the IGNOAPS under the Centre gives only INR 200-500 per month while the Indira Gandhi National Widow Pension Scheme (IGNWPS) gives only INR 300-500 per month which is less than 15% of both rural and urban MPCE.

A wage-to-pension contrast puts things into perspective. A single day of manual work under MGNREGA can out-earn an entire month of pension support. Multiple expert studies have suggested

PUTTING PENSIONS INTO PERSPECTIVE

According to the Periodic Labour Force Survey ⁺, female casual labourers earned an average of INR 306 per day⁵⁵ while the Indira Gandhi National Widow Scheme provides INR 300 per month.

⁺ As of April-June 2024

The average daily wage under MGNREGA is INR 266.1⁵⁴ ⁺ while the monthly pension under the Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme is INR 200.

⁺ As of 19th May 2025

reforms for better assistance⁵⁶ because pensions are crucial to ensure dignity and agency in later life. The minimum pension level is only 14.3% of the national poverty line, again, reflecting a significantly lower level of support. This is in stark contrast to other countries like Brazil where the minimum pension level stands at 220.4% of the national poverty line, offering substantial support to the elderly.

The pension rates of the Centre have not been revised for a long time and many states spend from their own purse to provide further support to the beneficiaries.

Several states, including Andhra Pradesh (*NTR Bharosa Pension Scheme*) and Karnataka (Pension for Physically Handicapped Persons - Above 75% Disability), provide welfare pensions that surpass central schemes in both absolute amounts and as a percentage of MPCE.

The monthly amount transferred under *NTR Bharosa Pension Scheme* to senior citizens, widows and other vulnerable groups is INR 4,000 per month totalling to INR 48,000 annually, which is 72% of the rural MPCE and 55% of the urban MPCE.

02

Special category pensions vary widely in generosity. Haryana has high provisions for differently-abled individuals at almost half of the MPCE (INR 3,000 per month) and acid attack victims at 89% of MPCE (urban) and 138% of MPCE (rural) (INR 7,500 - INR 13,500 per month). In contrast, Central schemes for similar groups remain capped at an abysmal INR 300 - INR

500 per month i.e. again less than 15% of MPCE.

03

Women-centred schemes have a broad range but are generally between 20-40% of rural and urban MPCE. UCT schemes like *Mukhyamantri Mahila Samman Yojana* (Delhi), *Lakshmir Bhandar* (West Bengal), and *Mahtari Vandan Scheme* (Chhattisgarh) fall within this range, indicating moderate financial assistance for recipients.

However, *Mukhyamantri Maiya Samman Yojana* in Jharkhand provides INR 2,500 per month, which amounts to 81.8% of rural MPCE and 45.8% of urban MPCE, significantly surpassing the typical range. This has been achieved by the state demonstrating notable progress in its fiscal standing,⁵⁷ through advancement in revenue mobilisation, strengthened fiscal discipline, and enhanced debt sustainability.

The disparities in the amounts transferred across schemes merits a deeper analysis about their adequacy. It underscores broader concerns for the sufficiency of India's welfare interventions.

While state-level enhancements improve financial security for certain groups, the underlying gaps in union schemes highlight systemic shortcomings in addressing poverty among vulnerable populations. This concern is further reinforced by recent studies on poverty measurement, which challenge existing estimations and argue for a reassessment of

benchmarks based on actual living costs.

Maitreesh Ghatak and Rishabh Kumar (2024)⁵⁸ delve into these perspectives, examining the implications of outdated poverty thresholds and the potential distortion caused by external policy interventions. They argue that the cost of meeting basic caloric intake based on the Indian Council of Medical Research's calorie norms (2,400 kcal rural; 2,100 kcal urban) and actual food prices from 2022-23 exceed the income levels of a significant portion of the population, suggesting a much higher true poverty rate than estimates. Furthermore, the study points to "accidental welfarism" — the continuation of pandemic-era food subsidies — as a key factor influencing household expenditure, possibly distorting poverty statistics.

Similarly, Crisil Intelligence⁵⁹ has found that the average cost of preparing a vegetarian *thali* at home is INR 26.3 and non-vegetarian *thali* is INR 53.9 in April, 2025. So, the cost of preparing 60 home-cooked vegetarian *thalis* a month is INR 1,578, while that of preparing the same number of non-vegetarian *thalis* is INR 3,234.⁵⁹ Therefore, a person needs to get at least INR 1,500 - INR 1,600 a month as an UCT only to cover the cost of an ordinary vegetarian meal, prepared at home.

While the state is not meant to cover all consumption expenses, there is merit in re-looking at poverty calculations to reflect current living costs, that can in turn serve as more effective benchmarks for scheme design.

POLICY COMMUNICATION AROUND UCTS

The public communication of welfare schemes should (a) clearly convey the goals and underlying values, and (b) resonate with the intended audience. Importantly, the narrative surrounding these schemes should **uphold the dignity and integrity of its recipients.**

For instance, Andrew Yang's proposal of the Freedom Dividend during the 2020 USA presidential campaign denoted the American ideals of individual liberty and choice through *freedom* while *dividend* emphasised an equitable distribution of national wealth for all Americans rather than cash aid.⁶⁰ The Freedom Dividend is a useful example of how the perception of welfare programmes is shaped by communication, with the framing often revealed by the scheme name itself.

In India, policymakers have frequently drawn on the country's deep-rooted cultural, religious, and societal values to frame policies and political campaigns. In our analysis of 81 conditional and UCT schemes across the country, we found that a broad majority of the names are meant to appeal to the recipient's cultural identity. Familial terms are especially

common in schemes for women and girls, with words like *behna*, *behen*, *ladki*, *maiya samman*, and *subhadra* signifying nurturance and care. **However, they also portray the government as a benefactor, inadvertently reinforcing gender-based hierarchies in society.**

Many livelihood-specific schemes incorporate terms like *mitra* or *nestham*, particularly in Andhra Pradesh, to suggest friendship or solidarity. For example, *YSR Law Nestham*, *YSR Nethanna Nestham*, and *YSR Rythu Bharosa*.

Our analysis also revealed a significant use of **cultural references** particularly through the names of influential figures from India's modern socio-political history, at the state level. For example, several DCT programmes in Maharashtra are named after Dr B.R. Ambedkar, reflecting his enduring legacy in the region. Similarly, many women-focussed CCTs in Tamil Nadu draw on the legacy of prominent social activists like Dr Muthulakshmi Reddy, Dr Saminathan Dharmambal, and Moovalur Ramamirtham Ammaiyar.

Many DCTs are named after popular social leaders and reformers to align with the values they stood for, and to re-inforce a sense of connection between the citizens and the state. Associations with current political figures serve a similar purpose, however, they are used less frequently.

In our analysis, only 24 of the 81 schemes used technocratic names. Educational subsidy schemes and targeted pension schemes most frequently carried technocratic names which conveyed the

intended recipients of the scheme while some CCTs referred to the objective of the scheme like inter-caste marriage assistance or financial help on the death of a family head.

PUBLICITY AND COMMUNICATIONS FOR KMUT IN TAMIL NADU⁶¹

The *Kalaingar Mahalir Urimai Thogai* (KMUT), introduced by the Tamil Nadu government in 2023, is aimed at financially empowering women and recognising their unpaid domestic and care work (UDCW).

The state provides INR 1,000 per month to eligible women over 21 years of age, with an annual household income of less than INR 2.5 lakh. The scheme was named *Urimai Thogai* (Rights Grant) to emphasise the notion of entitlement and to align with the broader goal of gender equality.

This intention was reflected in all the key publicity and communication for the implementation of KMUT. In their public addresses, the chief minister and the cabinet ministers, positioned the scheme as a recognition of women's UDCW, and highlighted its importance in improving women's living standards, self-respect, and agency. This intent was consistently shared through various channels of communication, and the scheme referred to its recipients as *Kudumba Thalaivi* or head of the household. This resonated with women; it instilled a sense of pride, and the government also issued ration cards in the name of women to align with this messaging.

Project DEEP has defined the design of schemes through four key components: Frequency, Amount, Communication, and Timing (F.A.C.T). There are various aspects that can be built upon and through this framework.

01

Inclusion of left behind

groups: Most schemes in India are targeted to specific demographics either universally within the group or further nuanced through means testing.

We see that a majority of the schemes are towards women, farmers and vulnerable groups. However, these individuals have **intersectional vulnerabilities** that need to be addressed. For example, street-dwelling women may access benefits under a woman-oriented scheme but that is not enough to meet her nuanced needs. Just the way a woman farmer can access both women- and farming-related schemes to meet a diverse set of requirements, other identities of various citizen groups including street dwellers, transpeople, prisoners under trial, and gig workers, need to be acknowledged and addressed through cash-based schemes.

One challenge is limited data availability, which hinders policy design. A 2019 survey on 'The State of Aadhaar' revealed that about 10 crore individuals, including 3 crore adults, did not have Aadhaar cards. A deeper look into this reveals that 30% and 25% of the group is constituted by street dwellers and transpeople respectively, with others including religious

minorities and scheduled tribes.⁴

An extensive and updated database of vulnerable groups, detailed needs assessment, and more creative implementation mechanisms given the complexity to identify and reach certain groups in real time, is required. Initiatives similar to the gender budget, started over two decades ago,⁶² are required at the national and state levels for other demographic groups, to monitor intentional inclusion.

02

Focusing on poverty alleviation and resilience:

While models enabling income smoothing and short-term consumption support have been established, more can be done to provide unrestricted access to capital for cash-poor communities to build foundational, long-term assets that can catalyse upward mobility and sustained transitions out of poverty.

This entails a fundamental shift from a safety net approach to one with **a trampoline effect**. It requires adopting innovative designs that enable immediate needs to be met, and addressing longer term financial requirements to build empowered, self-reliant, and resilient communities. This will lead to greater economic participation, boosting the overall growth multiplier of the country. It also has the potential to reduce future dependence on basic welfare, enabling greater focus on aspirational outcomes to further enhance wellbeing.

03

Examining amount adequacy:

There is no silver bullet to the question of amount efficacy. The current range is wide with monthly transfer schemes providing support from 10% to 200%+ of the average consumption.

Firstly, there is a need to **critically examine whether the existing amounts for UCTs are fulfilling the underlying objectives of the schemes**, for different demographics, through improved poverty and consumption estimates.

Secondly, a re-evaluation of the intended outcomes (as mentioned above) of cash-based policies is required to make more informed decisions about aspirational transfer amounts. There are studies that spotlight how asset ownership impacts spending patterns. Larger amounts improve risk appetite and disprove the myths of substance use and laziness. And finally there is the debate of universal amount for efficiency or tiered amounts to build equity. All these need more pilots to really understand the trade offs in terms of impact.

04

Portability of benefits:

Citizens who migrate for employment or other reasons are structurally excluded due to domicile-linked welfare. The idea of portability of benefits is inspired by social security in mobile populations. For example, 'One Nation One Ration Card' shows successful portability of food

entitlements across states. Social security platforms in the EU offer benefit continuity across member states. This concept needs to be applied to cash-based policies to ensure that vulnerable citizens are able to avail of schemes irrespective of their location of work or residence.

05

Integrating automatic stabilisers:

There is also space to mainstream and formalise the models that some state governments are adopting to provide ex-gratia payments for pollution bans, fishing bans, heat waves, and other kinds of natural disasters or calamities.

Cash transfers as a form of insurance, rehabilitation or adaptation have the potential to insulate vulnerable communities from fear and financial insecurity. Integrating these into formal mainstream policymaking is required for seamless rehabilitation of citizens post-crisis situations.

The frequency and timing of such models intended to provide relief and rehabilitation in the face of natural calamities would require **agile response mechanisms** to ensure timely support.

Various experiments have been conducted across the USA and Europe to analyse the impact of basic income on diverse demographics (street dwellers, new mothers, artists) and different outcome areas (poverty, mental health, health, rehabilitation). A similar breadth of extensive pilots is required in India to build local frameworks to guide intentional policy design that covers a larger population.

05

This section analyses the current implementation of direct cash transfers (DCT) across three stages. Namely, discovery, documentation, and delivery.

DISCOVERY Awareness

The first step to receiving benefits under any scheme is discovering it. Typically the government raises awareness through community drives, print, and digital media.

In 2022, Bal Krishna Mishra and Neekee Chaturvedi⁶³ studied the influence of print media in disseminating information about PM KISAN in the Gorakhpur district of Uttar Pradesh. They found that all the surveyed farmers were aware of the scheme with 85% demonstrating basic knowledge and 2.5% an advanced understanding. Newspapers emerged as the primary source of information (81.25%) followed by posters, pamphlets, and magazines. Notably, 92.5% of the respondents viewed the scheme positively, acknowledging its role in supporting agricultural activities (96.25%) and improving economic conditions (86.25%). About 88.75% found the financial assistance sufficient.

The idea of a family-level registry has been discussed in India for almost a decade now, to provide proactive welfare delivery to citizens, across schemes and a family's lifecycle. For example, as soon as someone turns sixty, their old-age pension should be activated automatically; and if someone is availing pension, they should also receive ration, since the income eligibility is the same for both.

ANKIT GOEL, VICE PRESIDENT,
SAMAGRA

DOCUMENTATION Enrolment and access

One needs to prove their identity and eligibility periodically to avail of DCTs. This is the first and most common roadblock in the process of accessing benefits because the enrolment centres can be hard to reach and the process only gets more long-winded when the operators-in-charge are absent or unavailable. Many people also face challenges with their paperwork if their Aadhaar cards are not properly linked to their bank accounts; if their KYC (Know Your Customer) process is incomplete;

and/or if their accounts are inactive or frozen. Resolving these challenges is cumbersome and time-consuming, particularly for those who live in remote and rural areas.

There has been a steady effort to streamline the enrolment process with the help of technology and improved citizen databases.

There is a movement towards state-level family databases that integrate data from various government departments to provide a comprehensive view of citizen interactions across programmes. This is the first step to more pro-active welfare delivery.

Some states like Haryana, Uttar Pradesh, and Rajasthan have adopted parts of this model. For example, Haryana has set up a Citizen Resource Information Department (CRID) to pro-actively reach out to those who are eligible for direct benefit transfers (DBTs) through a structured hierarchy that includes CRID officers, the DCRID, zonal officers, district officers, and local CRID volunteers. This ensures systematic engagement and service delivery across the state.

In Uttar Pradesh, the model is primarily implemented for revenue certificates like caste, domicile, and income—that are the most critical documents for accessing government schemes.

These databases help reduce manual fraud while streamlining access to services. Instead of requiring people to undergo lengthy verification processes repeatedly, their existing certificates—such as those held by their parents—automatically facilitate an application.

This simplifies the enrolment process for eligible applicants particularly in cases where entitlements are inherited by birth. Marriage can introduce some complexity but in most cases, the certificates can be issued instantly without forcing citizens to undergo a long bureaucratic process.

I think states are investing a lot of thought into [technology]. It's not just about the policy itself—if the outcome includes good datasets, strong interoperability, and better tech capabilities on the government's side, that would be a great outcome.

DR RAHUL KARNAMADAKALA SHARMA, DIRECTOR: LEARNING AND IMPACT, INDUS ACTION

DELIVERY

Withdrawal and grievance management

DCTs are sent to Aadhaar-linked bank accounts by the relevant authorities. This delivery mechanism, without middlemen, has reduced leakages and administration efforts. However, at the citizen-level some challenges persist. The payments can get delayed, skipped, or halted without prior notice or explanation. Further, one person may have multiple accounts and they may not know which is Aadhaar-seeded, and therefore accumulating benefits.

And finally, even if these challenges are managed, many people in rural and remote areas have poor access to financial institutions. They have to travel miles to withdraw their money and if the service point has

staffing issues it may, again, add to their fatigue in accessing benefits that are rightfully theirs.

Performance audits of various schemes as well as general audits by the Comptroller and Auditor General of India (CAG) from 2022 and 2023 reveal that states such as Odisha⁶⁴ and Sikkim⁶⁵ have not fully institutionalised the DBT Framework. A major hurdle is incomplete Aadhaar-seeding. For instance, in Odisha, 77% (2.42 lakh out of 3.13 lakh) of Post-Matric Scholarship recipients' bank accounts were not Aadhaar-seeded as of 2021.

Besides, scheme portals are often not modified to meet DBT requirements, and several states have failed to establish dedicated DBT cells. This lack of institutional preparedness leads to critical issues including delays in application processing; payments being sent to dormant, inactive, or incorrect accounts; and an increased risk of fraudulent withdrawals.

The reports also highlight persistent challenges related to the presence of intermediaries, particularly for pension schemes. This devolves DBTs into mere *benefit transfers*. For example, in Sikkim, the existence of multiple intermediaries caused delays in pension payment ranging from two days to 174.⁶⁵

Other process-related difficulties include a high percentage of delayed transactions (for example, 16% in MGNREGA in Sikkim) and the failure to re-initiate payments for beneficiaries when transactions fail, resulting in a loss of benefits.⁶⁵

A crucial component of trust is accountability to the last-mile citizen. There needs to be a mechanism through which the citizen can hold the system to task and receive answers from it. Accountability should go one step further—the learnings from those grievances should be fed back into the system to understand what kinds of improvements need to be made.

AISHWARYA NARAYAN, SENIOR RESEARCHER, DVARA RESEARCH

ROLE OF BUSINESS CORRESPONDENTS

Business or Banking Correspondents (BCs) play a critical role in the last-mile delivery of cash transfers (CTs) and financial inclusion particularly for marginalised populations. They serve as trusted intermediaries, helping citizens enrol in welfare schemes and facilitate Aadhaar-linked authentication. They are often the primary source of cash withdrawal in areas lacking formal banking infrastructure, acting as an information bridge between citizens and formal banking institutions.

However, there is a risk of individual fraud where excess money may be withdrawn without knowledge of the account owner and a **much larger organised fraud** based on the misuse of mass Aadhaar information.

The public and private sector are working on technology solutions like voice-box confirmations to mitigate these challenges but the risk of financial deceit and fraud continues, with recipients in remote areas being most vulnerable.

GRIEVANCE MANAGEMENT

The Department of Administrative Reforms & Public Grievances under the Union Government has a portal where individuals can file complaints related to NSAP pensions and other issues of public concern. In addition to the Union Government's efforts, several states have made significant progress in integrating grievance redressal mechanisms for their UCT schemes.

Some states have a centralised grievance redressal mechanism for their flagship schemes.

Providing multiple grievance redressal options—such as help desks, helplines, online platforms, and in-person assistance—can make the system more inclusive and accessible. This is particularly beneficial for those who are socio-economically disadvantaged and struggle to clearly express their concerns due to complex bureaucratic processes or communication barriers.

If you look at the experience of conditional or unconditional cash transfers from around the world, what really works is a bouquet of options for grievance redressal. Because sometimes relying on a single option can exclude people who may not be adept at using it.

SOUMYA KAPOOR MEHTA, SENIOR SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT SPECIALIST, SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT GLOBAL PRACTICE; LEAD: INDIA GENDER AND SOCIAL INCLUSION PLATFORM, WORLD BANK

THE CURIOUS CASE OF INOPERATIVE BANK ACCOUNTS

The Prime Minister's Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) had 10.34 crore inoperative accounts in December 2023 of which 4.93 crore belonged to women.

The deposited balance in the inoperative PMJDY accounts is around INR 12,779 crore which is around 6.12% of the total deposited balance in PMJDY accounts.

This balance continues to earn interest at par with operative accounts and can be withdrawn by the depositors at any time after the account becomes operative again. There can be many reasons for the accounts turning inoperational; it has no direct co-relation to the account-holder being untraceable.⁶⁶

ROLE OF DIGITAL PUBLIC INFRASTRUCTURE

Over the last 10 to 15 years, India has witnessed rapid growth in digital infrastructure, which has streamlined financial inclusion, reducing leakage in welfare programmes while enhancing targeting mechanisms for cash-based benefits.

However, DBTs still lack access to socio-economic data, limiting their ability to target households effectively. Integrating Aadhaar-based identifiers could facilitate seamless data exchange between various welfare schemes, ensuring more accurate beneficiary identification, says an International Monetary Fund Working Paper (2023).⁶⁷ Additionally, while financial inclusion has improved, the **frequency of transactions among women beneficiaries remains low**, indicating a gender divide in digital financial literacy. Inter-departmental data mobility and auto-validation mechanisms for welfare schemes were discussed

as critical improvements to ensure seamless service delivery.

Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI) has the potential to enhance the resilience and adaptability of social assistance programmes in India. One key initiative discussed was LocOS (People Operating System), developed by the Ministry of Rural Development to track financial transactions for over 100 million women beneficiaries engaged in self-help groups (SHGs).⁶⁸ The system integrates a resident database, eligibility verification mechanisms, and assisted enrolment features to optimise service delivery. By consolidating data across departments, it reduces duplication and ensures hyper-local insights for policymakers. Even in Andhra Pradesh, the State is increasingly adopting Grama/Ward Secretariat System to create real-time databases of citizen welfare access.

DPI implementation is cost-intensive and its adoption is influenced by political and bureaucratic dynamics, with policymakers focusing on citizen outreach while bureaucrats drive technical innovation.

As India progresses, DPI remains a key enabler for governance, balancing technology, human assistance, and policy evolution.

To effectively leverage DPI for social protection, there is a need for establishing robust data exchanges through a centralised social registry to facilitate bidirectional data flow and reduce exclusion errors. It is important to utilise data exchanges to raise scheme awareness, implement digital identity and data exchanges to streamline enrolment and registration processes, and create systems with smooth information flow to reduce transaction costs.

The introduction of the DBT Mission in 2013 with the aspiration of 'maximum governance and minimum government' has seen significant progress in the last decade. Delivery systems have been re-engineered to ensure simpler and faster flow of information and funds. Now, there is a need to build a more enabling ecosystem for citizens, to complement the government architecture.

01

Reducing access complexity:

While stringent KYC norms are required for efficient delivery, it often becomes a roadblock for accessing scheme benefits. This coupled with issues like spelling anomalies or mismatched fingerprints in Aadhaar can prevent individuals from accessing their entitlements or bank accounts, highlighting a critical need for streamlined and recipient-friendly processes.⁶⁹⁻⁷⁰

There can be additional incentives for business correspondents who provide services in underbanked areas that usually have a higher concentration of recipients to navigate the whole process from discovery to documentation and delivery. This can be supported by stringency against fraud, along with a mechanism to trace cash-based transactions.

This complemented with more states investing in unified family IDs to build a lifecycle approach into both design and delivery of schemes, will go a long way in ensuring that the cost and effort of accessing a scheme does not cannibalise the benefits it provides.

02

Infrastructure and technology:

The most important aspect of implementation that needs to be resolved is financial access. For instance, a quick look at the location of ATMs around major cities shows how the concentration reduces as one moves away from the centre, often stretching more than 20 kilometres between two points, in remote locations. Having points of service for enrolment, information, and withdrawal proximate to the recipients will significantly improve the schemes' impact. It will save time, effort, and most often daily wages that individuals forgo in the process of accessing their entitlements.

There should be mechanisms of live tracking of the application along with the specific reason for pendency/ rejection and the status of funds and reasons for delay, must be added to the beneficiary's online record across schemes; along with building requisite legal protection and ease of redressal.

Nodal DBT Cells are required to be set up in all implementing departments, for more focussed and coordinated execution of DBT schemes in the state and to ensure that lacunae pointed out in scheme implementation, are resolved in a timely manner.⁶⁴

Drawing from global best practices, digital technologies can enable innovative targeting approaches and streamline mass beneficiary registration, enhancing the reach and efficiency of social welfare programmes, while having robust privacy norms in place.

06

REACH

A rough estimate of the country's farmer-centric schemes* shows that they have reached ~4.37 crore agricultural households across various periods of time. That is nearly half of the total (~9.3 crore) as calculated in 2019.⁷¹

PM KISAN alone reached 9.8 crore farmers in February 2025.⁷²

The scheme has a wide reach across various states. For instance, during the 18th instalment (August 2024 - November 2024), Uttar Pradesh had the highest number of recipients at 2.26 crore, followed by Bihar with 0.76 crore.

* Rythu Bandhu (Telangana); Krishak Bondhu (West Bengal); CM Kisan (Odisha); Namo Shetkari Maha Samman Nidhi Yojana (Maharashtra); and YSR Rythu Bharosa (Andhra Pradesh)

Each coloured dot stands for 10,000 farmers who received benefits through the PM KISAN Yojana in 2025.

Similarly, women-centric schemes * are now reaching 10.7 crore women across different states. That is 16% of the total female population in India.⁷³

The scale of some women-focussed UCTs is quite large. For example, by December 2024, the Maharashtra government had deposited INR 17,505.90 crore into the bank accounts of 2.38 crore women under the *Mukhyamantri Majhi Ladaki Bahin Yojana*.⁷⁴ Likewise, *Kalaignar Mahalir Urimai Thogai* in Tamil Nadu reached an estimated 1.15 crore women by 14 February, 2025.⁷⁵

DID YOU KNOW

The *Mukhyamantri Majhi Ladaki Bahin Yojana* of Maharashtra reaches 2.38 crore women, which is more than the combined population of Cambodia, Singapore, and Brunei Darussalam!⁷⁶ Imagine an entire country solely populated by the recipients of this scheme — it would surpass the total population these three nations combined.

One critical part of the puzzle is money reaching the recipients on time, but we are also actively thinking—with our focus states—on how to shift the lens from subsistence to growth-oriented support, as contexts allow, to help families transition out of the poverty trap.

UJJWAL RELAN, VICE PRESIDENT,
SAMAGRA

* This assumes no beneficiary overlap, and excludes schemes for which reach data is not available. It includes *Lakshmi Bhandar* (West Bengal), *Namo Shri* (Gujarat), *Subhadra* (Odisha), *Indira Gandhi National Widow Pension Scheme* (Centre), *Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana* (Centre), *YSR Kapu Nestham* (Andhra Pradesh), *EBC Nestham* (Andhra Pradesh), *Mukhyamantri Majhi Ladaki Bahin Yojana* (Maharashtra), *Kalaignar Mahalir Urimai Thogai* (Tamil Nadu), *Ladli Behen Yojana* (Madhya Pradesh), *Gruhalakshmi* (Karnataka), *Mukhyamantri Maiya Samman Yojana* (Jharkhand).

OUTCOME & IMPACT ON PEOPLE'S LIVES

A Bayesian meta-analysis of 72 UCT programmes in middle and low income countries found positive and strong average treatment effects on a wide range of outcomes, irrespective of transfers being periodic or lumpsum: consumption, income, labour force participation, school enrolment, food security, psychological well-being, assets, and child height-for-age.⁷⁷ It also highlighted that UCTs encourage or at worst do not lower labour supply, debunking the notion that cash transfers discourage work.

It is crucial to study UCTs over an extended period of time to understand their longitudinal impact. But most of the schemes in India are relatively new except for the NSAP and state-level pensions and so they have been monitored

for reach rather than impact on household income, agricultural production, women's empowerment, social mobility and so on.

There is some early analysis by Artha Global⁷⁸ to show how households with low asset scores tend to use a substantial portion of any financial inflow—whether from small cash transfers or additional income—on essential consumption needs beyond food like electricity and water. They may also use the inflow to repay loans. When the household's asset score is relatively better, they are likely to already avail of higher-quality education, significant home improvements, and other discretionary services. Adding to this pool would require a substantial amount of money that is not met by direct transfers, and so the latter is primarily used to improve food consumption.

IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF VARIOUS PROGRAMMES

From the following pages

RYTHU BANDHU, TELANGANA

This scheme is meant to provide investment support to farmers through a cash transfer of INR 5,000 per acre for both crop cycles. Several studies indicate that this scheme has had a significant impact on agricultural production.

TARGETED

BI-ANNUAL

UNCONDITIONAL

- **Increased Investment in Inputs:** The UCT enables the farmers to invest in seeds, fertilisers, and pesticides without relying on high-interest loans.⁷⁹
- **Reduction of Debt Dependency:** The scheme has also helped them avoid private moneylenders thereby reducing their financial stress.⁸⁰
- **Higher Crop Productivity:** A study using a difference-in-differences framework found a positive and significant impact on agricultural output in terms of quantity and value of produce. However, the benefits were not uniform—medium and large-scale farmers reported greater improvements in comparison to small and marginal farmers probably due to differences in their investment patterns.⁸¹

Challenges in Sustainability:

While *Rythu Bandhu* has proved beneficial, there are concerns about the long-term viability of the scheme; its environmental impact; and the lack of emphasis on equity in the scheme design.⁸⁰

WORKFREE'S PILOT PROJECT, TELANGANA³⁹

The WorkFREE pilot was implemented with 1,250 people in four informal settlements in Hyderabad. The community, primarily dependent on waste-picking or domestic service, received an unconditional basic income (UBI) for 18 months. The money was provided to all members of the community including men, women, and children. The objective was to explore to what extent UBI can advance 'decent' work.

UNIVERSAL

MONTHLY

UNCONDITIONAL

- WorkFREE's pilot in Hyderabad had several positive effects in terms of the workers' material, social, and psychological condition. It improved their self-esteem, resilience, and aspirations.
- The participants could reduce the total number of hours spent on paid labour to dedicate more time to care-giving and other personal needs, with a steady inflow of funds. Their quality of life also improved with investments in assets like refrigerators, washing machines, and sturdier storage that reduce daily drudgery.
- The transfers also disrupted regular debt cycles, providing economic and psychological relief.
- Though it did not lead to a widespread exit from indecent work, owing to the structural factors that affect labour, the pilot has significant implications for policy. It can play a crucial role in re-framing the theoretical discussions on UBI as a strategy to provide people with greater agency over work.

It's not easy, sir, but we have to manage somehow. I get 2000 rupees as a widow and Amma [grandmother] gets 2000 rupees as pension. Now this (basic income) has come in so we can just about survive. Earlier I had to work or ask my brother but these days we can just about get by with this money.

FULL-TIME CARER, WOMAN,
HYDERABAD, TELANGANA

* Universal Cash Transfers are typically provided to the whole population in a defined administrative unit. While this pilot is restricted to a specific region, it is considered *universal* since the benefits are provided to everyone in the community. Further, it has been funded by philanthropic capital, which is typically used to create a proof of concept that can be later scaled up to the state or country level.

MUKHYAMANTRI MAJHI LADAKI BAHIN YOJANA, MAHARASHTRA (MMLBY)

Project DEEP conducted a survey in February 2025 with 100 recipients of MMLBY, which provides INR 1,500 per month to women from low-income households.

TARGETED

MONTHLY

UNCONDITIONAL

- It was observed that most households spend the money on food followed by savings and medical expenses.
- Most women were grateful for the financial support and freedom provided by the scheme.
- Some of them saved the money for contingencies and planned expenses like buying a cooler in the summer.
- The scheme provided a certain predictability of cash flows that enabled better planning and smoother consumption for those who have precarious wage cycles.
- For elderly women, who are unable to work, this money reduced their dependence on others for sustenance.
- Conversely, there were some women who mentioned that with the prices going up, this amount only enabled them to meet inflation, and there was no real difference in their lives.

Most importantly, MMLBY enabled women to fulfill everyday wishes that are often deprioritised in a bid to be thrifty. Some women treated themselves to a special snack; bought sarees or fulfilled their children's needs that are otherwise delayed.

At an aggregate level, we can surmise that the scheme has stabilised or improved people's marginal propensity to consume.

Now there is money in the bank. We can withdraw it whenever we need.

FARMER, WOMAN, GADCHIROLI,
MAHARASHTRA

PROJECT DEEP'S INTERVENTIONS, MAHARASHTRA AND RAJASTHAN³⁵

Project DEEP's programme entails a one-time, lumpsum cash transfer of INR 65,000 to all households in an economically-marginalised community. This transfer is meant to enable investments in long-term assets and livelihoods.

UNIVERSAL

ONE-TIME

UNCONDITIONAL

- Project DEEP's endline assessments with 501 households show that lumpsum transfers result in better economic outcomes; mental bandwidth; and standard of living for the recipients. This is primarily because of investments in long-term assets and livelihood enhancement.
- The villages that were primarily dependent on cash crops for their livelihood were able to enhance their agricultural activities without taking loans. This boosted their overall disposable income post harvest. Whereas those dependent on migration, preferred to invest in housing, land levelling and water, for which they can't typically save from their wages.
- In villages where people had foundational assets like land and housing, the funds were primarily used to enhance their livelihood by investing in livestock, better agricultural inputs, and entrepreneurial ventures. A significant portion of the funds was spent on housing in villages where most people live in kuchha houses.
- A lumpsum infusion also creates a multiplier effect. It leads to the circulation of capital in the local economy, benefitting smaller enterprises and job seekers.

These pilots show a clear hierarchy of needs; the provision of capital lends foundational support or works to unleash aspirations depending on the degree of vulnerability.

With the levelled land, we are already getting 2 to 3 extra quintals of wheat. Now this will be enough for the year, we will not have to buy more. We also repaid our loans and got our jewellery back, which is a huge relief.

FARMER, DUNGARPUR, RAJASTHAN

* Universal Cash Transfers are typically provided to the whole population in a defined administrative unit. While this pilot is restricted to a specific region, it is considered *universal* since the benefits are provided to everyone in the community. Further, it has been funded by philanthropic capital, which is typically used to create a proof of concept that can be later scaled up to the state or country level.

OUR TAKE

There is a significant amount of money being allocated to UCT schemes in India. However, their measurement is restricted at output (reach level). While there are early indications of state governments undertaking outcome and impact evaluations, there is a need for this to be done for more schemes in a rigorous manner, to enable data-backed policymaking.

Evaluation exercises must spotlight:

Spending patterns and change in consumption habits due to the availability of disposable income

Impact on the recipient's financial status and quality of life, and how this fares in relation to the scheme's objectives

Multiplier effects on the economy due to the infusion of cash and increase in purchasing power of consumers

Unintended consequences, both positive (debt levels, aspirations, spillover effects) and negative (inflation)

It is important to benchmark cash transfers to existing welfare schemes on both, cost efficiency and impact to optimise state finances and improve welfare delivery. This ties back to an outcome-based allocation of budgets in Section 3.

Additionally, it is also worth analysing the trade off between the costs incurred on implementation of such schemes and their impact.

This should be done keeping in mind recipients' ability to

participate in formal markets; larger terms of trade that the group operates within; and the existence of intersectional vulnerabilities that require social protection.

Such activities will also be instrumental in creating **feedback loops** that can inform scheme design in terms of amount and frequency as discussed in Section 4. They can also shed light on how citizens perceive different schemes, enabling policymakers to make more informed choices about welfare tools.

PERCEPTIONS OF UCTs

Through our interviews, we ascertained that the overall perspective on UCTs ranges from optimistic to sceptical. While some experts recognised cash transfers as a critical tool for enhancing welfare efficiency, reducing leakages, and empowering vulnerable groups, others offered a word of caution against excessive reliance on cash transfers without investing in education, healthcare, and infrastructure. Yet others were downright doubtful of the political motives behind the expansion of cash transfers, with fears about electoral gains being prioritised over genuine welfare.

Beyond that, there was a consensus that UCTs should not replace essential state functions but rather serve as strategic tools to enhance equity, reduce precarity, and improve welfare access. There must be investments in quality public goods like roads, schools, and hospitals so that citizens can use the money to enhance their lives. UCTs should not be a band-aid against broken systems.

While targeted cash transfers ensure resource efficiency, universal transfers are more appealing from a rights-based perspective.

Sustainability remains a key concern, and experts advocate for strong fiscal planning,

Welfare and UCTs

There is a general consensus that cash transfers should enhance welfare systems but must not replace essential public services like education, healthcare, and infrastructure. While there is a risk that over-reliance on UCTs may lead to weakening state responsibilities, it is still a crucial tool for reducing income precarity.

Amount and sustainability

There is a general understanding about balancing political salience, fiscal responsibility, and impact in order to design an effective scheme. However, even if benefit are primarily determined by the first two, any amount added to a vulnerable family's disposable income increases their marginal propensity to buy, creating a positive impact on consumption indicators.

Targeted versus universal transfers

One group strongly favoured targeted cash transfers as a way of ensuring equity and efficiency, especially given that ultra-poor households have diverse spending patterns across health, education, and debt repayment, while wealthier households tend to use UCTs for discretionary spending.

The other group advocated for universality from a rights-based perspective. They saw it as a means to mitigate inefficiencies, stigma, and political patronage.

Strategic fiscal allocation and trade-offs

Our respondents highlighted the constraints in fiscal spending, warning against excessive cash transfers that may divert resources from long-term development areas. While some support pragmatic allocations to cash transfers, others prefer different methods altogether like investments in agriculture research and development, and input subsidies.

DIGNITY

TRANSFORMATIONAL TOOL

ECONOMIC INDEPENDENCE

CATALYST FOR DEVELOPMENT

PURCHASING POWER

FREEDOM

LEGISLATED RIGHT

DELINK WORK AND SURVIVAL

MEANINGFUL LIVES

SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS

EMPOWERMENT

EFFICIENCY

EQUITY

CHOICE

AGENCY

This is our version of a word cloud. The size of each star and its corresponding word indicates how often the latter appeared in our interview transcripts.

Cash transfers have irreversibly changed the welfare system with their ability to reach people directly, with minimal leakage. Significant investments have been made in building the infrastructure to get this far and now it is time to move to the next stage of advancement with a bolder ambition: a more streamlined and just welfare portfolio. It will take collective effort from diverse stakeholders to shape the future of cash-based policies in India. Here is an overview of the actions they can take to strengthen fiscal management, design, implementation, and evaluation—all, to improve people's lives, down to the most remote mile.

FISCAL MANAGEMENT	DESIGN	IMPLEMENTATION	EVALUATION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Policymakers ● Academics <p>Analyse the performance of various welfare tools and remove or replace those that are not faring well in terms of cost and impact when compared to their original objectives and UCTs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Policymakers <p>Strengthen the data systems on which digital welfare relies. There is a dire need to correct and update our databases to reduce exclusion and to ensure people automatically receive benefits when they move from one life stage to another, or through crisis.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Policymakers <p>Invest in technology to improve targeting and to streamline mass beneficiary registration. These investments should be supported by an equal attention to digital privacy and protection.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Policymakers ● Non-profits ● Philanthropy ● Academics <p>Conduct or commission widespread, indepth, and objective evaluations of the cash-based schemes to understand their impact on individuals and the economy. The opportunity costs of intervening in free markets can also be measured to aid decisionmaking.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Non-profits ● Philanthropy <p>Undertake or support radical experiments and research-based pilots on cash transfers to inform policy design.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Non-profits <p>Continue to bridge the information asymmetry between citizens at the last mile and the government, while providing innovative solutions to improve welfare delivery</p>		

A niche segment of civil society has been the torchbearer of this movement for years. They started by developing proof of concepts, and dispelling the misbelief that cash leads to substance use, complacency, and laziness.

Now, as the government forges ahead, relying on evidence to use cash transfers for multiple challenges like malnutrition, inequity, and disempowerment, the question has moved from whether cash works to how it can be deployed most effectively to maximise impact.

It is time to join forces towards the common goal of providing a dignified future for all.

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ANNEXURE 1A - UCT SCHEMES

Scheme name, launch year, state, department, recipient, periodicity, annual amount per recipient

S.NO.	NAME	LAUNCH YEAR	STATE/CENTRE	PERIODICITY	DEPARTMENT	TARGET AUDIENCE	ANNUALISED AMOUNT*/RECIPIENT (IN INR)
1	National Family Benefit Scheme	1995	Centre	One Time	Ministry of Rural Development	Vulnerability-based	20,000
2	Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme	2007	Centre	Monthly	Ministry of Rural Development	Vulnerability-based	2,400 - 6,000
3	Indira Gandhi National Widow Pension Scheme	2009	Centre	Monthly	Ministry of Rural Development	Vulnerability-based	3,600 - 6,000
4	Indira Gandhi National Disability Pension Scheme	2017	Centre	Monthly	Ministry of Rural Development	Vulnerability-based	3,600 - 6,000
5	Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana	2019	Centre	Other	Ministry of Women and Child Development	Women	5,000 6,000
6	Pradhan Mantri Kisan Samman Nidhi	2019	Centre	Other	Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare	Farmers	6,000
7	DBT to PMJDY Women Account Holders	2020-21	Centre	Monthly	Ministry of Finance and Corporate Affairs	Women	1,500
8	NTR Bharosa Pension Scheme	2014	Andhra Pradesh	Monthly	Social Welfare, Tribal Welfare, Backward Classes Welfare, Minority Welfare	Vulnerability-based	48,000 - 1,80,000
9	YSR Matsyakara Bharosa	2019	Andhra Pradesh	Annual	Social Welfare, Tribal Welfare, Backward Classes Welfare, Minority Welfare	Livelihood-based	10,000
10	Rythu Bharosa	2019	Andhra Pradesh	Other	Department of Agriculture	Farmers	7,500
11	YSR Nethanna Nestham	2019	Andhra Pradesh	Annual	Social Welfare, Tribal Welfare, Backward Classes Welfare, Minority Welfare	Livelihood-based	24,000
12	YSR Jagananna Chedodu	2020	Andhra Pradesh	Annual	Social Welfare, Backward Classes Welfare, Minority Welfare, Tribal Welfare	Livelihood-based	10,000
13	YSR Kapu Nestham	2020	Andhra Pradesh	Annual	Social Welfare, Backward Classes Welfare	Vulnerability-based	15,000
14	EBC Nestham	2022	Andhra Pradesh	Annual	Backward Classes Welfare Department	Vulnerability-based	15,000
15	Swahid Kushal Konwar Sarbajanin Briddha Pension Achoni	2019	Assam	Monthly	Department of Panchayat and Rural Development	Vulnerability-based	3,000
16	Chief Minister's State Disability Pension Scheme	2019	Assam	Monthly	Women and Child Welfare Department	Vulnerability-based	18,000
17	Orunodoi	2020	Assam	Monthly	Finance Department	Women	15,000
18	Mukhyamantri Vridhjan Pension Yojna	2019	Bihar	Monthly	Department of Social Welfare	Vulnerability-based	4,800 - 6,000
19	Pension to Widows and Destitute Women	NA	Chandigarh	Monthly	Social Welfare, Women and Child Development Department of Chandigarh Government	Vulnerability-based	12,000
20	Minimata Mahtari Jatan Yojana	2010	Chhattisgarh	One Time	Labour Department	Women	20,000
21	Chief Minister Pension Scheme	2018	Chhattisgarh	Monthly	Social Welfare Department	Vulnerability-based	6,000
22	Mukhyamantri Shramik Siyaan Sahayata Yojana	2022	Chhattisgarh	One Time	Labour Department	Livelihood-based	20,000
23	Mukhyamantri Nirmaan Shramik Pension Sahayata	2023	Chhattisgarh	Monthly	Labour Department	Livelihood-based	8,400 - 18,000
24	Mahtari Vandan Scheme	2024	Chhattisgarh	Monthly	Department of Women and Child Development	Women	12,000
25	Social Security Pension Scheme	NA	Chhattisgarh	Monthly	Social Welfare Department	Vulnerability-based	6,000
26	Sukhad Sahara Yojana	NA	Chhattisgarh	Monthly	Social Welfare Department	Women	6,000
27	Griha Aadhar Scheme	2013	Goa	Monthly	Department of Women and Child Development	Women	18,000
28	Namo Shri Scheme	2024	Gujarat	One Time	Women and Child Development Department	Women	12,000

SR.NO	NAME	LAUNCH YEAR	STATE/CENTRE	PERIODICITY	DEPARTMENT	TARGET AUDIENCE	ANNUALISED AMOUNT*/RECIPIENT (IN INR)
29	Lado Lakshmi Yojana	2025	Haryana	Monthly	Department of Social Justice and Empowerment and the Department of Women and Child Welfare	Women	25,200
30	Total of State Schemes on Pensions	1980 onwards	Haryana	Monthly	Various departments	Vulnerability-based	30,000 - 2,00,000
31	Indira Gandhi Pyari Behna Sukh Samman Nidhi Yojana	2022	Himachal Pradesh	Monthly	Department of Social Justice and Empowerment	Women	18,000
32	Pension Under Social Security Schemes	NA	Himachal Pradesh	Monthly	Department of Social Justice and Empowerment	Vulnerability-based	9,000 - 18,000
33	Mukhyamantri Maiya Samman Yojana	2024	Jharkhand	Monthly	Department of Women, Child Development and Social Security	Women	30,000
34	Mukhyamantri Rajya Nirashrit Mahila Samman Pension Yojana	2024	Jharkhand	Monthly	Department of Women, Child Development and Social Security	Women	12,000
35	National Social Assistance Programme - NSAP (State Schemes)	NA	Jharkhand	Monthly	Women and Child Development and Social Security Department	Vulnerability-based	7,200 - 8,400
36	IGNOAPS (60-79 years) under Central Assistance Scheme	NA	Jharkhand	Monthly	Women and Child Development and Social Security Department	Vulnerability-based	12,000
37	IGNOAPS (80+ years) under Central Assistance Scheme	NA	Jharkhand	Monthly	Women and Child Development and Social Security Department	Vulnerability-based	12,000
38	IGNWPS under Central Assistance Scheme	NA	Jharkhand	Monthly	Women and Child Development and Social Security Department	Vulnerability-based	12,000
39	Indira Gandhi National Disability Pension Scheme (IGNDPS)	NA	Jharkhand	Monthly	Women and Child Development and Social Security Department	Vulnerability-based	12,000
40	Mukhyamantri Sarvajan Pension Yojana	NA	Jharkhand	Monthly	Women and Child Development and Social Security Department	Vulnerability-based	12,000
41	Gruhalakshmi	2023	Karnataka	Monthly	Department of Women and Child Development	Women	24,000
42	Pension under Social Security Schemes	NA	Karnataka	Monthly	Directorate of Social Security Pensions	Vulnerability-based	7,200 - 19,200
43	Samagra Samajik Suraksha Vridhavastha Pension Yojana	1981	Madhya Pradesh	Monthly	Department of Social Justice and Empowerment of Persons with Disabilities	Vulnerability-based	7,200
44	Ladli Behna Yojana	2023	Madhya Pradesh	Monthly	Department of Woman and Child Development	Women	12,000
45	Shravanbal Seva State Pension Scheme	2004	Maharashtra	Monthly	Department of Social Justice and Special Assistance	Vulnerability-based	4,800
46	Financial Assistance to 75% or Permanent Disability	2014	Maharashtra	One Time	Labour Department	Vulnerability-based	2,00,000
47	Sanjay Gandhi Niradhar Grant Scheme	2022	Maharashtra	Monthly	Department of Social Justice and Special Assistance	Vulnerability-based	7,200 - 10,800
48	Namo Shetkari Maha Samman Nidhi Yojana	2023	Maharashtra	Other	Agricultural Department	Farmers	6,000
49	Mukhyamantri - Majhi Ladki Bahin Yojana	2024	Maharashtra	Monthly	Department of Women and Child Development	Women	18,000
50	Financial Assistance for Widow or Widower of Registered Construction Worker	NA	Maharashtra	Annual	Labour Department	Vulnerability-based	24,000
51	Financial Assistance for Natural Death	NA	Maharashtra	One Time	Labour Department	Vulnerability-based	2,00,000
52	Mukhyamantri Mahila Samman Yojana	2024	NCT Delhi	Monthly	Department of Women and Child Development	Women	12,000
53	Krushak Assistance for Livelihood and Income Augmentation-KALIA (2018-19)/ CM KISAN (2024-25)	2018	Odisha	Other	Department of Agriculture and Farmers' Empowerment	Farmers	10,000-12,500
54	Subhadra	2024	Odisha	Annual	Department of Women and Child Development	Women	10,000

SR.NO	NAME	LAUNCH YEAR	STATE/CENTRE	PERIODICITY	DEPARTMENT	TARGET AUDIENCE	ANNUALISED AMOUNT*/RECIPIENT (IN INR)
55	Livelihood Support To Marine Fishermen During Fishing Ban Period	2016-17	Odisha	Annual	Fisheries and Animal Resources Development Department	Livelihood-based	15,000
56	Pensions under Social Security Schemes	NA	Punjab	Monthly	Department of Social Security, Women and Child Development	Vulnerability-based	2,400 - 20,000
57	Old Age Pension Scheme - Punjab	NA	Punjab	Monthly	Department of Social Security, Women and Child Development	Vulnerability-based	18,000
58	Dependent Children Pension Scheme - Punjab	NA	Punjab	Monthly	Department of Social Security, Women and Child Development	Vulnerability-based	18,000
59	Financial Help On Death Of Family Head	2008	Rajasthan	One Time	Department of Rural Development, Bhat Area Development	Vulnerability-based	10,000
60	Kalaingar Magalir Urimai Thittam	2023	Tamil Nadu	Monthly	Department of Social Welfare	Women	12,000
61	Rythu Bandhu	2018	Telangana	Other	Agriculture and Cooperation Department	Farmers	10,000 per acre
62	Maha Laxmi	2023	Telangana	Monthly	Telangana State Road Transport and Corporation	Women	30,000
63	Mukhyamantri Samajik Sahayata Prakaalpa	2022	Tripura	Monthly	Directorate Of Social Welfare and Social Education	Vulnerability-based	24,000
64	Mukhyamantri Samajik Sahayata Prakaalpa - Unorganized Workers	NA	Tripura	Monthly	Directorate Of Social Welfare and Social Education	Livelihood-based	24,000
65	Leprosy Pension Scheme	2017	Uttar Pradesh	Monthly	Department of Empowerment of Persons with Disabilities	Vulnerability-based	36,000
66	Divyang Pension Yojana	NA	Uttar Pradesh	Monthly	Department of Empowerment of Persons with Disabilities	Vulnerability-based	12,000
67	Manabik Scheme	2018	West Bengal	Monthly	Women and Child Development and Social Welfare Department	Vulnerability-based	12,000
68	Krishak Bandhu	2019	West Bengal	Other	Department of Agriculture	Farmers	4,000-2,00,000
69	Lakshmir Bhandar	2021	West Bengal	Monthly	Department of Women and Child Development	Women	12,000 - 14,400
70	Old Age Pension Scheme under Jai Bangla (JAIBANGLA)	NA	West Bengal	Monthly	Women and Child Development and Social Welfare Department	Vulnerability-based	12,000
71	Widow Pension Scheme under Jai Bangla (JAIBANGLA)	NA	West Bengal	Monthly	Women and Child Development and Social Welfare Department	Vulnerability-based	12,000

Notes

- * Where tiered benefits are available, the range is provided
Schemes meant for vulnerable women have been categorised as Vulnerability-based. For example, schemes meant for widows.
NA denotes not available
-
- Budgetary data is available for 51 schemes across different years, and 41 schemes in 2024-25 (BE)
- BE indicates Budget Estimate for the year 2024-25 when the budgets are announced at the national and state levels

Source: Budget documents of the Union and state governments (various years); [Economic Survey 2024 - 2025, Ministry of Finance](#); [myScheme \(Government of India's website\)](#)

SR.NO	NAME	BUDGETARY ALLOCATION IN INR CRORE													
		2011-2012	2012-2013	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-2024	2024-2025
31	Gruhalakshmi	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	17,500.0	28,608.4
32	Pension under Social Security Schemes	1,029.7	843.9	1,005.5	1,237.6	1,351.6	1,562.1	1,580.4	2,072.4	2,733.3	3,057.6	2,956.4	3,884.6	-	-
33	Samagra Samajik Suraksha Vridhavastha Pension Yojana	-	-	-	-	-	-	506.3	518.7	1,017.0	1,021.9	1,142.1	1,142.8	1,143.5	1,143.5
34	Ladli Behna Yojana	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	14,716.0	18,984.0
35	Shravanbal Seva State Pension Scheme	-	-	-	-	1,092.0	1,170.0	1,211.0	1,393.0	1,883.0	2,834.3	2,911.1	2,982.2	5,180.0	3,040.6
36	Sanjay Gandhi Niradhar Grant Scheme	-	-	-	-	642.0	709.0	719.0	866.0	1,170.0	1,516.0	1,568.8	1,689.0	2,781.2	1,810.0
37	Namo Shetkari Maha Samman Nidhi Yojana	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,512.0	1,000.0
38	Mukhyamantri - Majhi Ladki Bahin Yojana	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	46,000.0
39	Mukhyamantri Mahila Samman Yojana	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2,000.0
40	Krushak Assistance for Livelihood and Income Augmentation - KALIA (2018-19) / CM KISAN (2024-25)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	931.0	4,487.7	1,854.0	2,060.3	2,597.5	2,209.6	1,935.0
41	Subhadra	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10,000.0
42	Livelihood Support To Marine Fishermen During Fishing Ban Period	-	-	-	-	-	1.0	1.0	3.8	6.0	8.0	13.3	21.3	20.5	24.8
43	Pensions under Social Security Schemes	5.7	5.7	5.6	6.9	233.0	290.9	355.9	894.0	1,080.7	1,075.2	2,166.6	2,734.1	2,984.8	2,983.0
44	Kalaingar Magalir Urimai Thittam	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7,000.0	13,720.0
45	Maha Laxmi	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,082.5
46	Mukhyamantri Samajik Sahayata Prkalpa	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	24.0	72.0
47	Manabik Scheme	-	-	-	-	-	-	36.0	184.7	378.7	329.1	402.4	716.9	847.3	660.0
48	Krishak Bondhu	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,006.4	184.8	506.1	4,255.5	5,598.7	6,385.2	6,500.0
49	Lakshmir Bhandar	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,764.8	11,979.7	13,605.1	14,400.1
50	Old Age Pension Scheme under Jai Bangla (JAIBANGLA)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	562.5	1,060.9	1,933.1	2,350.8	3,701.0
51	Widow Pension Scheme under Jai Bangla (JAIBANGLA)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	256.0	475.9	1,685.9	2,205.5	2,040.0
	Total Allocation to UCT (INR CRORE)	1,035.4	1,018.8	1,215.8	1,505.7	12,188.3	16,976.3	21,126.7	28,621.6	85,287.0	1,32,651.2	1,16,660.5	1,26,598.6	1,85,964.5	2,80,780.5

Notes: BE indicates Budget Estimate for the year 2024-25 when the budgets are announced at the national and state levels

Source: Budget documents of the Union and state governments (various years); [Economic Survey 2024 - 2025](#), Ministry of Finance; [myScheme \(Government of India's website\)](#)

ANNEXURE 2 - COMPARISON TO OTHER SCHEMES & GDP

PARTICULARS	2011-2012	2012-2013	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-2024	2024-2025
Total allocation to UCTs (IN INR CRORE)	1,035	1,019	1,216	1,506	12,188	16,976	21,127	28,622	85,287	1,32,651	1,16,661	1,26,599	1,85,964	2,80,780
<i>Growth rate over previous years (%)</i>		-1.6	19.3	23.8	709.5	39.3	24.4	35.5	198.0	55.5	-12.1	8.5	46.9	51.0
National GDP (IN INR CRORE)	87,36,329	99,44,013	1,12,33,522	1,24,67,959	1,37,71,874	1,53,91,669	1,70,90,042	1,88,99,668	2,01,03,593	1,98,54,096	2,35,97,399	2,69,49,646	2,95,35,667	3,24,11,406
<i>UCT / GDP (%)</i>	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.09	0.11	0.12	0.15	0.42	0.67	0.49	0.47	0.63	0.87
States + Central social services spending (IN INR CRORE)						10,40,620	11,39,524	12,78,124	13,64,906	14,79,389	17,87,019	19,25,919	23,29,844	25,67,416
<i>UCT / social services spending (%)</i>						1.63	1.85	2.24	6.25	8.97	6.53	6.57	7.98	10.94
MGNREGA (IN INR CRORE)	29,215	30,275	32,994	32,977	37,341	48,215	55,166	61,815	71,687	1,11,170	98,468	90,806	89,154	86,000
<i>MGNREGA / GDP (%)</i>	0.33	0.30	0.29	0.26	0.27	0.31	0.32	0.33	0.36	0.56	0.42	0.34	0.30	0.27
Food subsidy, Centre (IN INR CRORE)					1,39,419	1,10,173	1,00,282	1,01,327	1,08,688	5,41,330	2,88,969	2,72,802	2,11,814	2,05,250
<i>Food subsidy / GDP (%)</i>					1.01	0.72	0.59	0.54	0.54	2.73	1.22	1.01	0.72	0.63
Total liabilities of Centre & States (IN INR CRORE)	58,84,548	66,27,820	75,33,161	83,00,583	94,38,248	1,05,84,410	1,18,90,383	1,33,30,025	1,51,21,885	1,77,37,834	1,98,98,951	2,22,30,475	2,46,18,349	
<i>Total liabilities of Centre & States / GDP (%)</i>	67.36	66.65	67.06	66.58	68.53	68.77	69.57	70.53	75.22	89.34	84.33	82.49	83.35	
Total outstanding liabilities of Centre (Internal + External) (IN INR CRORE)	46,70,054	52,25,307	58,59,331	64,11,391	70,98,298	76,25,078	84,54,631	93,77,857	1,05,55,487	1,24,23,016	1,39,02,763	1,56,16,855	1,72,69,017	1,85,43,428
<i>Total outstanding liabilities of Centre (Internal + External) / GDP (%)</i>	53.46	52.55	52.16	51.42	51.54	49.54	49.47	49.62	52.51	62.57	58.92	57.95	58.47	57.21

Note: BE indicates Budget Estimate for the year 2024-25 when the budgets are announced at the national and state levels

Source: Budget documents of the Union and state governments (various years); [Economic Survey 2024 - 2025](#), Ministry of Finance; [myScheme \(Government of India's website\)](#)

ANNEXURE 3 - STATE-WISE ANALYSIS

CENTRE / STATE / UNION TERRITORY	SCHEMES IDENTIFIED BY PROJECT DEEP	SCHEMES WITH BUDGETARY DATA AVAILABLE (2024 - 2025)	TOTAL UCT ALLOCATION (IN INR CRORE)	TOTAL STATE BUDGET (IN INR CRORE)	FISCAL DEFICIT 2023 - 2024 (IN INR CRORE)	HEADCOUNT RATIO AS PER MPI* (2019 - 2021)
Centre	7.0	5.0	69,621.9	4,820,512		
Andhra Pradesh	7.0	2.0	19,344.3	2,94,427	54,588	6.1
Arunachal Pradesh	0.0	0.0	0.0	35,465.0	2,515	13.8
Assam	3.0	1.0	3,800.0	1,43,891	20,957.0	19.4
Bihar	1.0	0.0	0.0	2,78,726	25,568.0	33.8
Chandigarh	1.0	0.0				
Chhattisgarh	7.0	3.0	3,556.8	1,56,801	15,194.0	16.4
Goa	1.0	1.0	199.2	26,631.0	4,308.0	0.8
Gujarat	1.0	1.0	750.0	3,28,447	44,930.0	11.7
Haryana	2.0	1.0	10,226.3	2,19,877	33,274.0	7.1
Himachal Pradesh	2.0	1.0	992.5	58,444.0	9,900.0	4.9
Jammu & Kashmir	0.0	0.0	0.0		12,081.0	
Jharkhand	8.0	6.0	10,584.7	1,28,900	11,675.0	28.8
Karnataka	2.0	1.0	28,608.4	3,71,383	66,646.0	7.6
Kerala	0.0	0.0	0.0	2,55,386	39,662.0	0.6
Madhya Pradesh	2.0	2.0	20,127.5	3,56,078	55,708.0	20.6
Maharashtra	7.0	4.0	51,850.6	6,69,491	95,501.0	7.8
Manipur	0.0	0.0	0.0	34,899.0	2,760.0	8.1
Meghalaya	0.0	0.0	0.0	27,072.0	1,592.0	27.8
Mizoram	0.0	0.0	0.0	14,277.0	1,247.0	5.3
Nagaland	0.0	0.0	0.0	23,728.0	1,121.0	15.4
NCT Delhi	1.0	1.0	2,000.0	76,000.0	10,386.0	3.4
Odisha	3.0	3.0	11,959.8	2,65,000	25,844.0	15.7
Puducherry	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	787.0	0.9

CENTRE / STATE / UNION TERRITORY	SCHEMES IDENTIFIED BY PROJECT DEEP	SCHEMES WITH BUDGETARY DATA AVAILABLE (2024 - 2025)	TOTAL UCT ALLOCATION (IN INR CRORE)	TOTAL STATE BUDGET (IN INR CRORE)	FISCAL DEFICIT 2023 - 2024 (IN INR CRORE)	HEADCOUNT RATIO AS PER MPI* (2019 - 2021)
Punjab	3.0	1.0	2,983.0	2,04,918	34,784.0	4.8
Rajasthan	1.0	0.0	0.0	4,95,467	62,772.0	15.3
Sikkim	0.0	0.0	0.0	14,003.0	2,147.0	2.6
Tamil Nadu	1.0	1.0	13,720.0	4,53,682	92,075.0	2.2
Telangana	2.0	1.0	3,082.5	2,91,159	56,063.0	5.9
Tripura	2.0	1.0	72.0	27,805.0	4,407.0	13.1
Uttar Pradesh	2.0	0.0	0.0	7,36,438	84,883.0	22.9
Uttarakhand	0.0	0.0	0.0	89,230.0	9,047.0	9.7
West Bengal	5.0	5.0	27,301.0	3,66,116	65,839.0	11.9
TOTAL	71	41	280,780			

Notes

*MPI = Multi-dimensional Poverty Index

Budgetary data as per 2024-25 (BE), State budget as per latest figures. BE indicates Budget Estimate for the year 2024-25 when the budgets are announced at the national and state levels

Source: Budget documents of the Union and state governments (various years); [Handbook of Statistics on Indian States 2024](#); [Survey on Household Consumption Expenditure \(2023 - 2024\)](#); [Fiscal Health Index 2022 - 2023](#), NITI Aayog

ANNEXURE 4 - COMPARISON TO MPCE

NAME OF SCHEME	CATEGORY OF RECIPIENT	STATE/ CENTRE	MONTHLY BENEFIT (IN INR)	AVERAGE MPCE WITH IMPUTATION (RURAL) IN 2023-24 (IN INR)	AVERAGE MPCE WITH IMPUTATION (URBAN) IN 2023-24 (IN INR)	AMOUNT AS % OF RURAL MPCE	AMOUNT AS % OF URBAN MPCE
DBT to PMJDY Women Account Holders	Pandemic response for three months in 2020	Centre	500	4,247	7,078	11.8	7.1
Indira Gandhi National Disability Pension Scheme	80 years and above	Centre	500	4,247	7,078	11.8	7.1
Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme	80 years and above	Centre	500	4,247	7,078	11.8	7.1
Indira Gandhi National Widow Pension Scheme	80 years and above	Centre	500	4,247	7,078	11.8	7.1
Indira Gandhi National Disability Pension Scheme	18-79 years	Centre	300	4,247	7,078	7.1	4.2
Indira Gandhi National Widow Pension Scheme	40-79 years	Centre	300	4,247	7,078	7.1	4.2
Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme	60-79 years	Centre	200	4,247	7,078	4.7	2.8
NTR Bharosa Pension Scheme	Completely disabled	Andhra Pradesh	15,000	5,539	7,341	270.8	204.3
NTR Bharosa Pension Scheme	Suffering from Chronic Kidney Disease, including thalassemia	Andhra Pradesh	10,000	5,539	7,341	180.5	136.2
NTR Bharosa Pension Scheme	Partial disabled	Andhra Pradesh	6,000	5,539	7,341	180.3	81.7
NTR Bharosa Pension Scheme	Old Age Persons, Widow, Toddy Tappers, Weavers, Single women, Fishermen, ART (PLHIV) Persons , Traditional Cobblers, Transgender & Dappu Artists;	Andhra Pradesh	4,000	5,539	7,341	72.2	54.5
Chief Minister's State Disability Pension Scheme	People with a disability of 40% or more, between 18-59 years of age	Assam	1,500	3,961	6,913	37.9	21.7
Orunodoi	Women from low income households	Assam	1,250	3,961	6,913	31.6	18.1
Swahid Kushal Konwar Sarbajanin Briddha Pension Achoni	Senior citizens of Assam	Assam	250	3,961	6,913	6.3	3.6
Mukhyamantri Vridhjan Pension Yojna	Individuals whose age is 80 years and above	Bihar	500	3,788	5,165	13.2	9.7
Mukhyamantri Vridhjan Pension Yojna	Individuals who are in the age group of 60-79 years	Bihar	400	3,788	5,165	10.6	7.7
Pension To Widows And Destitute Women	Widows And Destitute Women	Chandigarh	1,000	8,857	13,425	11.3	7.4
Mukhyamantri Nirmaan Shramik Pension Sahayata	Construction workers above 60 years	Chhattisgarh	1,500	2,927	5,114	51.2	29.3
Mahtari Vandan Scheme	Eligible married women	Chhattisgarh	1,000	2,927	5,114	34.2	19.6
Mukhyamantri Nirmaan Shramik Pension Sahayata	Widow of construction workers	Chhattisgarh	700	2,927	5,114	23.9	13.7
Chief Minister Pension Scheme	Senior citizen, widows and abandoned women	Chhattisgarh	500	2,927	5,114	17.1	9.8
Social Security Pension Scheme	People with disabilities	Chhattisgarh	500	2,927	5,114	17.1	9.8
Sukhad Sahara Yojana	Widows and deserted women	Chhattisgarh	500	2,927	5,114	17.1	9.8
Griha Aadhar Scheme	Housewives and homemakers from economically weaker sections	Goa	1,500	8,178	9,782	18.3	15.3
State Schemes on Pension	Financial Assistance to Acid Victims (>60% disability)	Haryana	13,500	5,449	8,462	247.8	159.5
State Schemes on Pension	Financial Assistance to Acid Victims (51-60% disability)	Haryana	10,500	5,449	8,462	192.7	124.1
State Schemes on Pension	Citizens who actively participated in the 1975 emergency and faced imprisonment	Haryana	10,000	5,449	8,462	183.5	118.2

NAME OF SCHEME	CATEGORY OF RECIPIENT	STATE/ CENTRE	MONTHLY BENEFIT (IN INR)	AVERAGE MPCE WITH IMPUTATION (RURAL) IN 2023-24 (IN INR)	AVERAGE MPCE WITH IMPUTATION (URBAN) IN 2023-24 (IN INR)	AMOUNT AS % OF RURAL MPCE	AMOUNT AS % OF URBAN MPCE
State Schemes on Pension	Financial Assistance to Acid Victims (40-50% disability)	Haryana	7,500	5,449	8,462	137.6	88.6
State Schemes on Pension	Destitute Women and Widows	Haryana	3,000	5,449	8,462	55.1	35.5
State Schemes on Pension	Destitute Women and Widows (Scheduled Caste)	Haryana	3,000	5,449	8,462	55.1	35.5
State Schemes on Pension	Differently abled persons	Haryana	3,000	5,449	8,462	55.1	35.5
State Schemes on Pension	Differently abled persons (Scheduled Caste)	Haryana	3,000	5,449	8,462	55.1	35.5
State Schemes on Pension	Social security for families with only daughters once either parent reaches 45 years of age	Haryana	3,000	5,449	8,462	55.1	35.5
State Schemes on Pension	Social security for families with only daughters once either parent reaches 45 years of age (Scheduled Caste)	Haryana	3,000	5,449	8,462	55.1	35.5
State Schemes on Pension	Pension to Transpersons	Haryana	3,000	5,449	8,462	55.1	35.5
State Schemes on Pension	Ex-Servicemen and their widows above the age of 60 years	Haryana	3,000	5,449	8,462	55.1	35.5
State Schemes on Pension	Orphan children of ex-servicemen	Haryana	3,000	5,449	8,462	55.1	35.5
State Schemes on Pension	Disabled ex-service men	Haryana	3,000	5,449	8,462	55.1	35.5
State Schemes on Pension	Blind ex-service men	Haryana	3,000	5,449	8,462	55.1	35.5
State Schemes on Pension	War Widows of Defence Forces Personnels	Haryana	3,000	5,449	8,462	55.1	35.5
Total of State Schemes on Pensions, in crores	Pension to Aged Physically Handicapped and Destitute Women & Widows Staff at District Level	Haryana	3,000	5,449	8,462	55.1	35.5
State Schemes on Pension	Individuals of 60 years and above	Haryana	2,500	5,449	8,462	45.9	29.5
State Schemes on Pension	Individuals of 60 years and above (Scheduled Caste)	Haryana	2,500	5,449	8,462	45.9	29.5
Lado Lakshmi Yojana	Women above 18 years	Haryana	2,100	5,449	8,462	38.5	24.8
Indira Gandhi Pyari Behna Sukh Samman Nidhi Yojana	Women between 18-59 years of age	Himachal Pradesh	1,500	5,833	9,230	25.7	16.3
Pension Under Social Security Schemes	Pensioners aged between 70 years and above	Himachal Pradesh	1,500	5,833	9,230	25.7	16.3
Pension Under Social Security Schemes	Individuals with 80% or more disability	Himachal Pradesh	1,300	5,833	9,230	22.3	14.1
Pension Under Social Security Schemes	Widow pension	Himachal Pradesh	1,000	5,833	9,230	17.1	10.8
Pension Under Social Security Schemes	Pensioners aged between 60 years to 69 years	Himachal Pradesh	850	5,833	9,230	14.6	9.2
Pension Under Social Security Schemes	Leprosy patients	Himachal Pradesh	750	5,833	9,230	12.9	8.1
Mukhyamantri Maiya Samman Yojana	Women aged 21-49 years, permanent residents of Jharkhand	Jharkhand	2,500	3,056	5,455	81.8	45.8
Central Assistance Scheme - IGNWPS (top up)	Individuals between 60-79 years of age	Jharkhand	1,000	3,056	5,455	32.7	18.3
Central Assistance Scheme - IGNWPS (top up)	Individuals 80 years and above	Jharkhand	1,000	3,056	5,455	32.7	18.3
Central Assistance Scheme - IGNWPS (top up)	Widows of 40 years and above	Jharkhand	1,000	3,056	5,455	32.7	18.3

NAME OF SCHEME	CATEGORY OF RECIPIENT	STATE/ CENTRE	MONTHLY BENEFIT (IN INR)	AVERAGE MPCE WITH IMPUTATION (RURAL) IN 2023-24 (IN INR)	AVERAGE MPCE WITH IMPUTATION (URBAN) IN 2023-24 (IN INR)	AMOUNT AS % OF RURAL MPCE	AMOUNT AS % OF URBAN MPCE
Indira Gandhi National Disability Pension Scheme (IGNDPS)	Persons with disabilities - 18 years and above	Jharkhand	1,000	3,056	5,455	32.7	18.3
Mukhyamantri Rajya Nirashrit Mahila Samman Pension Yojana	Women whose husband has died, abandoned women, single women aged 45 years or more	Jharkhand	1,000	3,056	5,455	32.7	18.3
Mukhyamantri Sarvajan Pension Yojana	Elderly individuals, widows, destitute women, differently-abled persons, primitive tribes, and HIV/AIDS patients	Jharkhand	1,000	3,056	5,455	32.7	18.3
National Social Assistance Programme - NSAP (State Schemes) - IGNOAPS	Individuals 80 years and above	Jharkhand	700	3,056	5,455	22.9	12.8
National Social Assistance Programme - NSAP (State Schemes) - IGNDPS	Persons with disabilities between 18-79 years of age	Jharkhand	600	3,056	5,455	19.6	11.0
National Social Assistance Programme - NSAP (State Schemes) - IGNOAPS	Individuals between 60-79 years of age	Jharkhand	600	3,056	5,455	19.6	11.0
National Social Assistance Programme - NSAP (State Schemes) - IGNWPS	Widows between 40-79 years of age	Jharkhand	600	3,056	5,455	19.6	11.0
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Endosulfan Victim Pension	Karnataka	4,000	5,068	8,169	78.9	49.0
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Acid Victim Pension	Karnataka	3,000	5,068	8,169	59.2	36.7
Gruhalakshmi	Women heading households	Karnataka	2,000	5,068	8,169	39.5	24.5
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Farmer Widow Pension	Karnataka	2,000	5,068	8,169	39.5	24.5
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Pension for Physically Handicapped Persons - Above 75% Disability	Karnataka	1,600	5,068	8,169	31.6	19.6
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Individuals between 65-79 years of age	Karnataka	1,200	5,068	8,169	23.7	14.7
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Individuals between 80 years and above	Karnataka	1,200	5,068	8,169	23.7	14.7
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Senior citizens above 65 years of age in unorganised sectors	Karnataka	1,000	5,068	8,169	19.7	12.2
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Pension for Physically Handicapped Persons - Above 40% and less than 75% Disability	Karnataka	800	5,068	8,169	15.8	9.8
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Destitute Widow Pension	Karnataka	800	5,068	8,169	15.8	9.8
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Unmarried and divorced women between 40-64 years of age, below the poverty line	Karnataka	800	5,068	8,169	15.8	9.8
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Individuals between 60-64 years of age	Karnataka	600	5,068	8,169	11.8	7.3
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Sexual minorities	Karnataka	600	5,068	8,169	11.8	7.3
Ladli Behna Yojana	Married,widowed, divorced and abandoned women in the age brackets of 23-60 years	Madhya Pradesh	1,250	3,522	5,589	35.3	22.4
Samagra Samajik Suraksha Vridhavastha Pension Yojana	Destitute elderly individuals who lack financial support and are unable to sustain themselves	Madhya Pradesh	600	3,522	5,589	17.0	10.7
Mukhyamantri - Majhi Ladki Bahin Yojana	Women aged 21 to 65 years	Maharashtra	1,500	4,249	7,415	35.3	5.4
Sanjay Gandhi Niradhar Grant Scheme	If multiple beneficiaries in the family	Maharashtra	900	4,249	7,415	21.2	5.4

NAME OF SCHEME	CATEGORY OF RECIPIENT	STATE/ CENTRE	MONTHLY BENEFIT (IN INR)	AVERAGE MPCE WITH IMPUTATION (RURAL) IN 2023-24 (IN INR)	AVERAGE MPCE WITH IMPUTATION (URBAN) IN 2023-24 (IN INR)	AMOUNT AS % OF RURAL MPCE	AMOUNT AS % OF URBAN MPCE
Sanjay Gandhi Niradhar Grant Scheme	If one beneficiary in the eligible family	Maharashtra	600	4,249	7,415	14.1	5.4
Shravanbal Seva State Pension Scheme	65 years or above in age, whose family is listed as Below Poverty Line	Maharashtra	600	4,249	7,415	14.1	5.4
Shravanbal Seva State Pension Scheme	65 years or above in age, whose family is listed as Below Poverty Line	Maharashtra	400	4,249	7,415	9.4	5.4
Mukhyamantri Mahila Samman Yojana	Female citizens of Delhi between 18-60 years of age (promised)	NCT Delhi	2100	7,415	8,548	28.3	24.6
Mukhyamantri Mahila Samman Yojana	Female citizens of Delhi between 18-60 years of age	NCT Delhi	1,000	7,415	8,548	13.5	11.7
Dependent Children Pension Scheme	Dependent children	Punjab	1,500	5,874	7,383	25.5	20.3
Old Age Pension Scheme	Men above 65 years of age, and women above 58 years of age	Punjab	1,500	5,874	7,383	25.5	20.3
Pensions under Social Security Schemes	Individuals between 60-69 years of age	Punjab	1,500	5,874	7,383	25.5	20.3
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Financial Assistance to Widows and Destitute Women	Punjab	1,500	5,874	7,383	25.5	20.3
Pensions under Social Security Schemes	Financial Assistance to Dependent Children	Punjab	1,500	5,874	7,383	25.5	20.3
Pension under Social Security Schemes	Financial Assistance to Disabled Persons	Punjab	1,500	5,874	7,383	25.5	20.3
Kalaignar Mahalir Urimai Thittam	Women above 21 years of age	Tamil Nadu	1,000	5,872	8,325	17.0	12.0
Maha Laxmi	Women from low income households	Telangana	2,500	5,675	9,131	44.1	27.4
Mukhyamantri Samajik Sahayata Prakaalpa	Vulnerable women, including widows, deserted, unmarried, and those needing special care or protection	Tripura	2,000	6,368	8,118	31.4	24.6
Mukhyamantri Samajik Sahayata Prakaalpa	Unorganized Workers	Tripura	2,000	6,368	8,118	31.4	24.6
Leprosy Pension Scheme	Family income below the poverty line	Uttar Pradesh	3,000	3,578	5,474	83.8	54.8
Divyang Pension Yojana	Family income below the poverty line	Uttar Pradesh	1,000	3,578	5,474	27.9	18.3
Lakshmir Bhandar	For women from Scheduled Caste / Scheduled Tribes households	West Bengal	1,200	3,815	5,903	31.5	20.3
Lakshmir Bhandar	Women from other category	West Bengal	1,000	3,815	5,903	26.2	20.3
Manabik Scheme	Disabled persons who are unable to work	West Bengal	1,000	3,815	5,903	26.2	16.9
Old Age Pension Scheme under Jai Bangla (JAIBANGLA)	Individuals above 60 years of age	West Bengal	1,000	3,815	5,903	26.2	16.9
Widow Pension Scheme under Jai Bangla (JAIBANGLA)	Widows	West Bengal	1,000	3,815	5,903	26.2	16.9

Note: The values of rural and urban monthly per capita expenditure are based on the Household Consumption Expenditure Survey (August 2023 - July 2024).

Source: Budget documents of Union and state governments; [myScheme \(Government of India's website\)](#); [Factsheet Household Consumption Expenditure Survey \(August 2023 - July 2024\)](#), Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MoSPI)

ANNEXURE 5 - REACH DATA

NAME OF SCHEME / PROGRAMME	INDIA/STATE	NO. OF RECIPIENTS, LATEST AVAILABLE	AS OF
DBT to PMJDY Women Account Holders	Centre	Over 20 crore women ⁸²	2020
Indira Gandhi National Disability Pension Scheme (IGNDPS)	Centre	8.3 lakh ⁸³	22/04/2025
Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme (IGNOAPS)	Centre	221.3 lakh ⁸³	22/04/2025
Indira Gandhi National Widow Pension Scheme (IGNWPS)	Centre	67.8 lakh ⁸³	22/04/2025
National Family benefit Scheme (NFBS)	Centre	4.8 lakh (approximately) ⁸³	22/04/2025
National Social Assistance Programme (umbrella scheme for IGNOAPS, IGNWPS, IGNDPS & NFBS)	Centre	302.8 lakh ⁸³	22/04/2025
PM KISAN	Centre	Over 9.8 crore farmers including 2.41 crore female farmers ⁸⁴	24/02/2025
Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana	Centre	Beneficiaries Enrolled: 24.1 lakh Beneficiaries Paid: 16.4 lakh ⁸⁵	Till 26/03/2025
EBC Nestham	Andhra Pradesh	4.2 lakh poor women belonging to Reddy, Kamma, Arya Vysya, Brahmin, Kshatriya, Velama and other OC communities ⁸⁶	14/03/2024
NTR Bharosa	Andhra Pradesh	No. of pensions disbursed: 61.9 lakh ⁸⁷	22/04/2025
Rythu Bharosa	Andhra Pradesh	81.9 lakh farmers ⁸⁸	Not mentioned
YSR Jagananna Chedodu	Andhra Pradesh	3.3 lakh eligible beneficiaries ⁸⁹	30/01/2023
YSR Kapu Nestham	Andhra Pradesh	3.6 lakh eligible women beneficiaries of Kapu, Balija, Telaga and Ontari communities ⁹⁰	16/09/2023
YSR Matsyakara Bharosa	Andhra Pradesh	1.2 lakh ⁹¹	April 15 to June 14, 2023
YSR Nethanna Nestham	Andhra Pradesh	Over 6.7 lakh weavers and artisans enrolled ⁹²	01/01/2022
Orunodoi	Assam	37.2 lakh beneficiaries ⁹³	19/09/2024
Mukhyamantri Vridhjan Pension Yojna	Bihar	51.6 lakh ⁹⁴	22/04/2025
Pension To Widows and Destitute Women	Chandigarh	0.09 lakh beneficiaries ⁹⁵	01/02/2021
Namo Shri Scheme	Gujarat	Over 6 lakh women ⁹⁶	18/02/2025
Financial Assistance to Acid Victims	Haryana	10 ⁹⁷	2023-24
Financial Assistance to Destitute Women and Widow	Haryana	8.2 lakhs ⁹⁸	2023-24
Ladli (Social Security Pension Scheme)	Haryana	0.35 lakhs ⁹⁹	2023-24

NAME OF SCHEME / PROGRAMME	INDIA/STATE	NO. OF RECIPIENTS, LATEST AVAILABLE	AS OF
Old Age Samman Allowance Scheme	Haryana	17.85 lakh beneficiaries ¹⁰⁰	20/12/2024
Pension to Differently Able Person	Haryana	2.1 lakhs ¹⁰¹	24/01/2025
Pension to Eunuchs	Haryana	39 ¹⁰²	2023-24
Provision for financial assistance to widows of ESM not in receipt of family pension	Haryana	0.58 lakhs ¹⁰³	31/12/2024
Provision for Orphan children of ESM	Haryana	100 ¹⁰⁴	2023-24
Shubhra Jyotsna Pension Scheme	Haryana	501 ¹⁰⁵	25/06/2024
Mukhyamantri Maiya Samman Yojana (2024)	Jharkhand	Over 56.6 lakh women ¹⁰⁶	01/01/2024
Mukhyamantri Sarvajan Pension Yojana	Jharkhand	40 lakh beneficiaries ¹⁰⁷	21/10/2024
Gruhalakshmi	Karnataka	1.25 crore beneficiaries: 93.7 lakh other category beneficiaries, 22.6 lakh Scheduled Caste beneficiaries and 8.8 lakh Scheduled Tribe beneficiaries ¹⁰⁸	End of July, 2024
Ladli Behna Yojana	Madhya Pradesh	1.31 crore ¹⁰⁹	22/04/2025
Mukhyamantri - Majhi Ladki Bahin Yojana	Maharashtra	2.38 crore women ¹¹⁰	07/03/2025
Namo Shetkari Maha Samman Nidhi Yojana	Maharashtra	1.15 crore farmer families ¹¹¹	02/09/2024
Mukhyamantri Mahila Samman Yojana	National Capital Territory of Delhi	Estimated 45-50 lakh women; final numbers yet to be determined ¹¹⁰	21/04/2025
KALIA	Odisha	64.8 lakh beneficiaries: 45.7 lakh are Small & Marginal Farmers and 19.1 lakh are Landless Agriculture Households ¹¹²	24/07/2024
Livelihood Support To Marine Fishermen During Fishing Ban Period	Odisha	0.15 lakh fishing family across the marine districts of Bhadrak, Ganjam, Kendrapada, Jagatsinghpur, and Puri in Odisha ¹¹³	01/02/2024
Subhadra	Odisha	Over 98 lakh women ¹¹⁴	04/03/2025
Pensions under Social Security Schemes	Punjab	The Punjab Government gave pensions to 22.68 lakh elderly beneficiaries until December 2024. This does not include other beneficiaries. ¹¹⁵	01/12/2024
Kalaingar Magalir Urimai Thogai	Tamil Nadu	1.15 crore beneficiaries ¹¹⁶	14/02/2025
Maha Laxmi	Telangana	Beneficiaries of this scheme have availed 149.63 crore trips aboard 7,227 buses free of charge ¹¹⁷	19/03/2025

NAME OF SCHEME / PROGRAMME	INDIA/STATE	NO. OF RECIPIENTS, LATEST AVAILABLE	AS OF
Rythu Bandhu Scheme	Telangana	70 lakh farmers ¹¹⁸	26/06/2023
Mukhyamantri Samajik Sahayata Prakalpa - Unorganized Workers	Tripura	0.30 lakh eligible beneficiaries ¹¹⁹	05/02/2024
Divyang Pension Yojana	Uttar Pradesh	10.7 lakhs beneficiaries of Divyang Pension Scheme ¹²⁰	04/04/2020
Leprosy Pension Scheme	Uttar Pradesh	0.12 lakhs beneficiaries ¹²¹	03/08/2024
Krishak Bondhu	West Bengal	Nearly 1.05 crore farmers and sharecroppers under Krishak Bandhu (Natun) scheme ¹²²	01/06/2024
Lakshmir Bhandar Scheme	West Bengal	1.98 crore ¹²³	08/02/2024

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